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RIGOUROUS -

secuRe desIGn and deplOyment of trUsthwoRthy
cOntinUum computing 6G Services

Deliverable 3.1

**DESIGN PLAN OF THE MULTI-DOMAIN AUTOMATED
SECURITY ORCHESTRATION, TRUST-MANAGEMENT,
AND DEPLOYMENT**

Title	Design plan of the multi-domain automated security orchestration, trust-management, and deployment
Document description	This deliverable will report the initial outcomes coming from all the tasks in WP3, including the first analysis and design of the enablers and components for automated security orchestration, the design of the human-centric tools, open security and privacy models, the trust management as well as end-to-end slicing across multiple domains and network segments. [M12, R, PU, UWS]
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Explanation/ Definition
5G	5 th Generation Mobile networks
6G	6 th Generation Mobile Networks
6G-NR	6G New Radio interface
AF	Application Function
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
AMQF	Advanced Message Queueing Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
AS	Access Stratum
AUSF	Authentication Server Function
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf
CPU	Central Process Unit
DCS	Default Credentials Server
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DHCP	Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol
DoS	Denial of Service
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit
DPI	Deep Packet Inspection
DSC	Dynamic Service Composer
DU	Distributed Unit
E2E	End to End
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
FL	Federated Learning
GENEVE	Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation
GRE	Generic Routing Protocol
GTP	GPRS Tunnelling Protocol
HSPL-OP	High-level Security Policy Language for Orchestration Policies
I2NSF	Interface to Network Security Function
IKE	Internet Key Exchange Protocol

IoT	Internet of Things
IODEF	Incident Object Description Exchange Format
IPSec	Internet Protocol Security
ISM	Intend-based Security Management
JSON	Java Script Object Notation
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MSK	Master Session Key
MSPL	Management Specification Language
MSPL-OP	Medium-level Security Policy Language for Orchestration Policies
MTD	Moving Target Defence
MUD	Manufacturer Usage Description
NAI	Network Access Identifier
NAS	Non-Access Stratum
NBI	North Bound Interface
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NFV MANO	Network Function Virtualization Management and Orchestration
NRF	Network Repository Function
PCF	Policy Control Function
PCO	Protocol Configuration Option
QoS	Quality of Service
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAN	Radio Access Network
ReMUI	Response Mitigation User Interface
RiMUI	Risk Management User Interface
RM	Response Mitigation
SAD	Security Association Database
SBI	Service Based Interface
SDN	Software Defined Networks
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SM	Slice Manager
SMD	Security Management Domain

SMUI	Security Formal Modelling User Interface
SO	Security Orchestrator
SP	Security Policy
SPD	Security Policy Database
SSLA	Security Service Level Agreement
STIX	Structured Threat Information Expression
SUCI	Subscription Concealed Identifier
TC	Traffic Control
TESF	Trust Evaluation and enabler Service Function
TRA	Thread Risk Assessor
UE	User Equipment
UPF	User Plane
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communication
URN	Uniform Resource Name
URSP	UE Route Selection Policy
VM	Virtual Machine
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VSF	Virtual network Security Function
VXLAN	Virtual eXtensible Local Area Network
XDP	Express Data Path
XML	Extensible Markup Language
YAML	Yet Another Mark Language
ZTM	Zero Trust Management

Table 1. List of abbreviations and acronyms.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the first iteration of the research, design, implementation, and modular testing of the enablers and components aimed to achieve AI-driven multi-domain automated security orchestration, end-to-end slicing, human-centric DevSecOps and zero trust-management for 6G system. It encompasses the activities focused on achieving the project objectives on holistic framework, human-centric DevSecOps, and AI-driven security orchestration.

In particular, this deliverable describes the initial design and prototyping of the following solutions:

- Human-centric security and privacy modelling and quantification for DevSec operations.
- DevSec user-friendly tools.
- Onboarding specifications for network resources and devices:
 - Adaptive deployment mechanisms by relying on on-the-fly resources provisioning and orchestration.
- Zero-trust security management.
- Enablers to accomplish End-to-End multidomain multitenant 6G slicing.
- Multi-domain security orchestration by applying corrective actions and counter measurements to detected security and privacy breaches to reduce risk.

In addition, the next steps for the second iteration are presented.

The assets and the RIGOUROUS architectural components involved in WP3 are grouped in 4 categories according to their functionality and the services they provide in the context of multi-domain security orchestration, trust-management, and deployment.

- The assets related to human-centric and privacy modelling and onboarding focus on continuous deployment using CI/CD and DevPrivOps practices, onboarding of the RIGOUROUS network applications and their specifications and intend based creation of network slices. Regarding the onboarding specification, an NFV security onboarding specification evolved from OpenSlice is presented, introducing a richer interface and specifications capturing security and privacy dimensions. Regarding policy-based security network management, RIGOUROUS introduces a multi-level abstraction approach providing new functionalities such as Network Slicing and Federated Learning Monitoring. This approach will enable a more streamlined security management, automation, deployment, and configuration in multi-domain infrastructures. The Policy Framework offers a dynamic plugin-based service able to translate high-level policies into specific infrastructure specifications as part of the Security Management Domain orchestration. Different policy models are designed and discussed such as Filtering Policy, Channel Protection Policy, Network Slicing Policy, and Federated Learning.

- Assets dealing with AI-driven cross-domain security and privacy orchestration are focused on the design and implementation of a multi-domain multi-tenant orchestrator covering zero-touch device bootstrapping, trusted application onboarding and secure orchestration of entities at the network edge. RIGOUROUS provides an AI-driven policy-based security orchestrator that will ease security management in highly complex, challenging, and diversified infrastructures such as 5G and beyond. Different AI algorithms will be deployed across domains and across different E2E network segments such as IoT devices, RAN, Edge, Core, and Cloud. A Federated Learning approach will be followed to provide improved security orchestration capabilities that will empower dynamic provisioning, deployment, and reconfiguration of the virtual network security functions. To best optimize orchestration for all critical assets, different methods are applied to determine the optimal location to deploy a security policy. Different system variables and constraints are considered such as network latency, trade-off and constraint management, resource allocation or, location awareness. Regarding the IoT bootstrapping and onboarding, the design of the zero-touch device bootstrapping and the trusted application is presented. It enables a secure connection setup of the IoT devices with long-term credentials as well as to prevent harmful applications for being installed in the IoT devices. Privacy-preserving Attribute-Based Credentials (p-ABC) are used in RIGOUROUS as digital credentials providing minimal disclosure, unlinkability and trustworthy certification of attributes.
- Concerning zero trust and smart security management, first, it has been conducted a state-of-the-art analysis of the existing trust evaluation and management techniques, data sharing, and authentication methods used in 5G. Then, after considering the associated requirements, it has been defined the functionalities and services that the RIGOUROUS Trust Evaluation framework has to provide to achieve abnormal behaviour-based security evaluation and monitoring and to use gained insight for security policy generation and fine-grained access control. A first architectural design of the trust evaluation and enabler service function is introduced using a distributed approach across the network and management domains. To conclude this category, it is provided the workflow for data collection and security evaluation result notification for a target such as core NF.
- The last category is composed by the RIGOUROUS assets in charge of providing E2E multi-domain and multi-tenant network slicing capabilities as a mitigation security mechanism. It involves providing slicing enablers for both RAN and non-RAN network segments. ORO is the partner providing a realistic infrastructure to validate and evaluate the use cases related to network slicing. In ORO's testbed, the NOKIA 5G CORE is used to provide core network functions and the NOKIA Aircscale Cloud is deployed for RAN management. With respect to multi-domain testbed, ORO will provide two different interconnected 5G infrastructures located in Bucharest and Lasi. To tackle the complexity inherent in 5G networks, the RIGOUROUS Slice Manager asset will provide a technology-independent approach for data plane programmability, thus offering agile and efficient network slicing management. The enablers responsible for the enforcement of security policies in the data plane as network slices are required to handle encapsulated traffic characteristic of overlay networks expected in virtualized multi-tenant environments. In RIGOUROUS, this capability

is provided by the Network Self-Protection asset. In addition, the interaction between the different components involved in the E2E NS process has been analysed and described in a sequence diagram. To conclude this category, aspects related to multidomain, alignment with other tasks and alignment with the use cases where Network Slicing as a mitigation technique will be empirically validated and evaluated.

Each category comprises a section within this document. Within each section, based on the development stage of each of the WP3 assets, a first design is presented including, where relevant, sequence diagrams, component architectural diagrams, protocols and technologies used and innovations when compared to the current state of the art. Furthermore, both functional and non-functional requirements identified for each component are described.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1. Background and Overview

This deliverable presents the design and first prototyping phase outcomes of WP3 multi-domain automated security orchestration, trust-management, and deployment, focusing on the research and development of the major components in the RIGUROUS architecture. In WP2, the high-level RIGUROUS architecture is being defined, with information models, APIs, and Interfaces, which allow the integration of the components from WP3 into the architecture. In this deliverable, the components design, information models, APIs and interfaces are further specified in the scope of WP3, especially through the initial design of the primary workflows in each of the 4 tasks. In addition, the relation to relevant use-case scenarios, as defined in WP2, is also further addressed in the context of the components per task.

The outputs of each task undertaken as part of WP3 will contribute to the fulfilment of both functional and non-functional requirements identified and collected in D2.1 and aligned with the scope of the project.

The functional requirements describing the desired behaviour of each of the RIGUROUS components involved in WP3 are presented at the beginning of the corresponding section covering each of the tasks (Sections 4 to 7 for tasks T3.1 to T3.4).

Regarding non-functional requirements, the RIGUROUS architectural components developed as outcomes of the tasks in this work package shall satisfy requirements concerning security, design, and implementation. Regarding security-related non-functional requirements, WP3 will provide a trust evaluation framework to monitor, verify and identify trusted applications enabling a secure end-devices bootstrapping. With respect to design-related non-functional requirements, WP3 will provide an interoperable and flexible security model. Finally, as implementation-related non-functional requirement, WP3 will deliver a technology-agnostic network slicing mechanism enabling the enforcement of slices in the data plane regardless the inherent complexity of the underlying physical and virtualised infrastructure. Thus, this novel approach by hiding the technology-dependant features of the multiple network devices and technologies comprising the data plane, will provide an abstraction layer and enhanced programmability of the data plane.

This deliverable provides the status of the first outcomes from tasks T3.1, T3.2, T3.3, and T3.4. A brief description of the goal for every task is provided below:

- **T3.1:** This task entails the design and development of human-centric security, placing behavioural and cognitive features at the forefront of beyond 5G (B5G)/6G security processes, policies, procedures, and guidelines, with the goal of achieving transparency, measurable security, and privacy. Specifically, the necessity to target the appropriate information to convey perceived risk (e.g., attack surface), evaluate ongoing threats (e.g., unauthorized scanning for vulnerabilities), and report the efficacy of any defence

mechanisms in place to mitigate those threats (e.g., Moving Target Defence (MTD) mechanisms or additional countermeasures).

- **T3.2:** AI-driven cross-domain Security and Privacy orchestration in IoT-edge-cloud continuum involves designing an AI-driven orchestration system for seamless, scalable, and flexible IoT-edge-Core cloud continuity in 6G to enable automatic deployment of infrastructures and bootstrapping IoT devices. This system will also provide self-recovery capabilities and coordinate actions to reduce attacks on services and infrastructure.
- **T3.3:** Zero trust and Smart security management using a Trust evaluation and enabler service framework (TESF) to ensure security and trustworthiness of the 6G systems. The framework includes subscribe/unsubscribe service, direct/indirect trust data collection, and recommended actions (e.g., related to security enforcement) for trusted services.
- **T3.4:** End-to-End multi-domain multi-tenant 6G network slicing capabilities focused on the design of novel network slicing mechanisms enabling a fine-grain control of the network traffic and demonstrating cyber-attack resilience.

Figure 1 presents a high-level view of the RIGOUROUS architectural components involved in the End-to-End Network Slicing Control and Management. In the upper part of Figure 1, the management layer is composed of the RIGOUROUS functional components dealing with tasks such as:

- Security and privacy policy modelling tools based on a Human-Centric approach,
- Orchestration of services and resources for IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum,
- Zero trust and Smart security management, and
- E2E Network slice management and enablers.

This RIGOUROUS components are outcomes from Task 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 and they collaborate with the aim of applying a set of Security Policies (SPs) and Security Service Level Agreements (SSLAs) related policies which will be implemented in the infrastructure as an End-to-End (E2E) Network Slicing. The output of the management layer is a technology-independent message sent from the Security Orchestrator to the Slice Manager (SM) with the information needed to enforce an E2E network slice in the 6G infrastructure.

The E2E Network Slicing Control and Management Layer consists of the components and services enabling the network slicing capabilities. The E2E slice manager is a centralized component acting as North Bound Interface (NBI) with the upper management layers. The Slice Controllers are distributed sub-components of the slice manager providing the logic needed to cope with the different underlying technologies used by the Security Agents in the data plane where the network slice will be deployed. The communication between the Slice Manager API and the different Slice Controllers is established via a middleware message broker such as RabbitMQ based on AMQP (Advanced Message Queue Protocol).

Figure 1. High Level view of RIGOUROUS components involved in WP3.

Finally, the lower part of *Figure 1* depicts an overview of the different network segments composing a multi-tenant 6G physical infrastructure where the network slices will be enforced: Radio Access Network (RAN), Edge, Transport, Core and Multi-Domain and Internet Gateway. From left to right, the 6G UEs and IoT devices are connected to Distributed Units (DU) via the 6G New Radio (6G-NR) interface. The DUs provide connectivity to the Edge network segment. The edge is considered the last mile, close to the final users, where commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) equipment can provision different components of the 6G architecture. The infrastructure provider relies on virtualisation to provide support for multi-tenancy, that is, multiple virtualised tenants sharing the same physical infrastructure and resources. Notice in *Figure 1* how different Virtual Machines (VMs) owned by different tenants are allocated both in the edge and in the core segments.

The CUs deal with the management of the radio interface, user handover, and security, among others (referred as gNB). The edge is connected to the core by a transport network. The core network is a traditional cloud computing infrastructure. In *Figure 1*, the 6G core has a set of User Plane Functions (UPFs) responsible for forwarding the user data across the data path and a set of control and management functions in charge of authentication, user mobility, handover management, user registry, and so on. Finally, the interdomain segment connects the mobile network operator domain to other domains and provides access to the Internet.

2.2. Relation to Project Objectives

The objectives of this deliverable are in line with the objectives of WP3 and the overall project objectives, especially Objective 1 Holistic Smart Service framework for securing the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum lifecycle management, Objective 2 Human-Centric DevSecOps, and Objective 3 Model-based and AI-driven Automated Security Orchestration, Trust Management, and deployment. In particular, this deliverable aims to achieve the following:

- In relation to Objective 1, based on D2.1, this deliverable further develops the functional architecture of the framework by specifying the architecture of multi-domain orchestration.
- In relation to Objective 2, this deliverable describes the design and prototyping of the human-centric security and privacy modelling and onboarding.
- In relation to Objective 3, this deliverable describes the design and prototyping of the AI-driven orchestration, zero-trust security management, and end-to-end multi-domain network slicing.

2.3. Organisation of the Document

The rest of the document is structured as follows:

- Section 3 presents the overall architecture and approach.
- Sections 4 to 7 describe in detail the first iteration of the key solutions, focusing on the main outcomes from the four tasks in WP3 respectively.
- Section 8 outlines the next steps for the second iteration.
- Section 9 concludes this deliverable.

3 OVERALL ARCHITECTURE AND APPROACH FOR MULTI-DOMAIN AUTOMATED SECURITY ORCHESTRATION, TRUST-MANAGEMENT AND DEPLOYMENT

This section describes the overall functional architecture of WP3, in line with the RIGOROUS reference architecture developed in D2.1 as shown in *Figure 2*.

Figure 2. RIGOROUS High-level Functional Block Architecture (HLFA).

At Design Plane, the architecture covers different parts of DevSecOps paradigm, including mechanisms for automatic enforcement of security policies defined by administrators, software developers or security operators within the network. Thus, the architecture should support a model-driven approach for DevSecOps definition. In this regard, the architecture might consider conflict detection mechanisms across different kinds of security and orchestration policies in heterogenous 6G domain. The main functional components at design level, covered in WP3 are the following ones:

- Human Controllable Privacy (PUI):** This user interface (UI) serves as the project's interface responsible for demonstrating the degree of privacy protection offered by the services analysed through the privacy quantification model. The integration of privacy risk management models is planned within the context of a specialized DevOps framework referred to as DevPrivOps. Within this framework, privacy quantification models will continuously assess the privacy level of a specific network service in real-time. This privacy

assessment adopts a user-centric approach by presenting a simple and user-friendly scale that enables any user to comprehend the associated privacy risks. The PUI will make this scale accessible to both developers and end-users.

- **Intent Based security formal modelling (SMUI):** these tools are intended for administrators and operators to define, in a user-friendly way, the security policies and intents aimed to rule the security operations in the network.
- **App Onboarding Specification (AOUI):** Provides management services to configure the Policy Control Function (PCF) with operator managed trusted applications specific information to further enable the PCF to provision the application configuration to the UE for application verification.

WP3 takes care of the enablers and tools needed for device/app onboarding, the network/security management based on policies and DevSecOps approach, trust, security orchestration and security enforcement, including network slicing mechanisms. To this aim, the architecture is endowed with a Zero-Trust Security and Identity Management component that shall be instantiated through different services for trust evaluation and enabler service framework (TESF) related functionalities to perform continuous trust evaluation of entities or functions (i.e., including Physical network functions (PNFs) and Virtual network functions (VNFs)) at the RAN and Core, application functions and end-user devices associated to the network), trust quantification and validation to ensure minimization of potential impacts, such as security breach, lateral threat movement and service failure.

In order to cover the NIST.SP.800-207 [\[1\]](#) Zero Trust cybersecurity paradigm adapted to 5G, RIGOROUS should describe trust service which can enable continuous trust validation (i.e., monitoring the state) and minimization of impacts (i.e., if any security breach occurs), where the trust service will consider various factors including behavioural/environmental attributes, monitoring/measuring the integrity or security posture of the involved function or entity. As millions of devices are expected to be connected in 6G, the architecture, as part of the Trust and Identity Management, should consider verifiable secure identification with privacy preservation and pseudonymization (i.e., with digital identifiers such as decentralized identifiers/self-sovereign identifiers) for UE onboarding to different network services over 6G.

The Trust evaluation and enabler service of the ZTM shall consider various factors, such as monitoring data including behavioural or environmental attributes, monitoring the integrity or security posture of the involved function or entity in the communication system, potential service violations, malicious operations, to evaluate the trustworthiness and to estimate the service reliability and resilience of the target under trust evaluation (i.e., a function or entity which is under trust evaluation/being evaluated is referred as 'Target'). To this end, trust evaluation and enabler service might apply AI algorithms for trust related evaluation analytics and predictions. Based on the evaluated trust information, the TESH can provide notifications to the trust service consumers. Any network or application function which consumes or provides services, to and from the evaluation target, can subscribe to the trust service as consumer to get proactive notifications about the trustworthiness of the target. The trust service consumers might utilize the trust data notification to determine and allow/deny further service consumption or service provision, respectively, for the target. In case a target is evaluated to have less trust or is compromised, the trust service consumer can invoke potential network operation (e.g., reassignment of serving

network functions for the end user or for the network service consumers as applicable) to ensure the service continuation (i.e., for the end-users and the network functions respectively). The trust data can also be utilized by the operator to configure network management functions to isolate and fix the security issues (e.g., vulnerabilities) of the evaluated target. Moreover, to ensure trust and security adaptations, the ZTM component might enable the Identity and Access control Management services that should guarantee privacy and verifiable security identification of devices in hostile scenarios set up with high number of IoT devices deployed at the edge of the 6G Network, and in the scenarios where the end-users require temporary network as-a-service access.

The Security Orchestrator deals with allocation decision inferring the physical and virtual function chaining and actions to be enforced cross-level, cross-network segments, and cross-domains to enforce the intents. The orchestrator might be driven by AI to make their chaining and orchestration decision and should rely on special modules to translate the intents, policies and behavioural profiles coming from the decision into concrete actions. To this aim, AI algorithms might run across-domains and cross network-segments IoT-RAN-EDGE-Core-Cloud in the 6G network. The orchestrator might also decide best actions for re-configuring, during operation, the virtual network security functions and associated low-level intents and policies. To this aim, the security orchestrator shall consider among others, network parameters such as Quality-of-Service (QoS) capacities, security, and network capabilities, actual resources CPU, RAM, storage, system status, and current deployed policies. The orchestrator might interface with the Response and Mitigation module of the reaction plane and directly with other Managers, such as Slice Manager to enforce certain countermeasures such as isolating the potential attacker traffic in a slice.

The following functional components of the architecture are being designed and developed in the scope of WP3:

- **Zero trust and identity management (ZTM):** Zero Trust management is a security approach that focuses on minimizing access to network assets and resources, based on authentication, authorization, and security posture of the requestor. This approach proposes event-based data collection to identify security risks and threats. This allows operators to evaluate and monitor security results, enabling the creation of access control policies that enforce fine-grained access control to prevent threat lateral movement. The RIGOUROUS Framework offers a Zero Trust Management function that collects event information related to violations of normal behaviours, service requests, critical configuration changes, load, status, and resource utilization. This data is then provided to the Operator's security evaluation and monitoring function, which receives security monitoring results in the form of trust data. The main capability is related to the collection of Network Functions related data from the Network Repository Function (NRF).
- **AI driven security orchestrator (SO):** This functional block is responsible for enforcing security requirements through virtual network security functions (VSF) and the service enforces security policies for the local domain, deploying necessary security agents through Intent-Based Security Management (ISM), Slice Manager, or NFV MANO. It can also orchestrate policy enforcements on multiple domains to cover security configuration requirements. This allows SO to respond automatically to actual contexts and prevent

future threats. It receives mitigation policies from the AI-driven Decision Engine. The SO communicates with other functional blocks, such as the ISM for conflict detection, NFV MANO for deployment, Zero Trust Identity Management for trust scores, and the Slice Manager for security end-to-end slices. The main capability is to enforce or remove security policies.

- **Intent based security management (ISM):** The functional block transforms abstract Protection Level and Security Level requirements into specific parameters for AI-driven Security Orchestrators. It provides a framework for defining Security Service Level Agreements (SSLAs), refines them into deployment-ready representations, enforces them in real time, and enables conflict detection.
- **Slice Manager:** The functional block allows the user to create new customized End-to-End network slices across the network infrastructure, and to trigger the enforcement of such slices into the infrastructure after the calculation of the different endpoints.
- **Security agents:** The network self-protection functional block is in charge of performing the performance isolation of the network slices into the data path. To do so, it makes use of several technologies such as OpenVSwitch (OVS) or Network Filtering agents.

4 HUMAN-CENTRIC SECURITY AND PRIVACY MODELLING AND ONBOARDING: FIRST ITERATION

In the scope of the applications deployed into the 6G RIGOUROUS infrastructure, those are considered to be developed following the best practices regarding CI/CD and DevPrivOps. The publishing step makes the resources available at a resource catalogue, so that they can be later instantiated into a specific network slice. The human centric security and privacy modelling and onboarding will consider several steps as described below:

- Continuous development with focus on developing services composed of functions that are privacy aware with a DevPrivOps approach. These functions have clear data gathering and processing and security specifications, which later can be used for quantification of their privacy impact, optimizing deployment, or providing a more transparent view over the data processing behaviour.
- Onboarding into the 6G RIGOUROUS catalogue, where the network applications, and their specifications are registered. The specification of a network application includes standard descriptors, as provided by solutions such as OpenSlice¹, but will also include information regarding the data processing and other security characteristics/requirements. One example of the security characteristics may relate to technical aspects of the endpoints to facilitate Security-Orchestration-Automation-Response (SOAR) processes, or Mutation through MTD. These follow the same format and enhance the network application with more information required for the secure instantiation and application of the RIGOUROUS mechanisms.
- Intent based creation of a slice, making use of a set of resources (Applications/Network Functions), which provides a final service for users to connect. The Security and Privacy specification of the applications is combined with the slice specification, keeping a transparent and privacy aware data processing flow.

The onboarding specification evolves from OpenSlice, as it suits the base purpose of the RIGOUROUS approach and intends to enhance it through richer interface and specifications that can capture the security and privacy dimensions. *Figure 3* depicts the overview of onboarding defined by OpenSlice, and also demonstrates the integration with the remaining architecture.

¹ <https://openslice.io>

Figure 3. High level diagram overview of the onboarding components.

In this onboarding architecture, the following components are enhanced for the use cases of 6G RIGOROUS:

- The NFV Privacy and Security Specification: A novel specification for VNFs and (by extension) Network Services within the ETSI NFV framework, which exposes characteristics relevant for security and for privacy, building upon (and going further) than the work already validated in the community.
- The Service and Security Specification: A novel specification for Network Services, which combines the typical service definition with enhanced data processing and security controls.
- The Enhanced Human Centric Services UI: An enhanced version of the UI supporting the definition of the additional specifications.
- The Enhanced Human Centric VNF Catalogue Management Web UI: An enhanced version of the previous UI, which support security and privacy definitions, enabling the remaining components to assess and implement the correct security mechanisms.
- The Privacy Quantifier component: which takes in consideration the service and NFV descriptions, as well as other input from users and metadata, to compute the privacy impact of an entity. This is vital for components such as the PUI.
- The Enhanced Human Centric Services UI component is considered as part of the PUI and enables service providers in designing services where the privacy impact is estimated at design time. Existing components from solutions such as *Openslice* are taken into consideration, extending them to the case where privacy scoring, and security resilience aspects are provided. With this information and taking in consideration the NFV available in the catalogue, it is possible to build security and privacy focused services. The cases where variations of the same service may exist are considered. These variations may be a subset of features without additional security or enhanced privacy controls.

4.1. Security and Privacy Specifications

4.1.1. NFV Security Onboarding Specification

The NFV Security Onboarding Specification follows the requirements previously specified in D2.1 and creates the interfaces that allow delivering the data models with respective configurations/policies that fulfil the requirements.

Fulfilling the requirements demands that the Security Onboarding can be done via the Intent-based Security Formal Modelling (SMUI) or via the Security Orchestrator (SO) in their respective data formats. The Risk Model is onboarded via the Risk Management UI (RiMUI) into the Threat Risk Assessor (TRA) using its data format. Similarly, the Response Playbooks are onboarded via the Response-Mitigation Policies (ReMUI) into the Response-Mitigation (RM) using specific data models. Service Composition is possible via the SCUI that will onboard the Service Composition Description into the Dynamic Service Composer (DSC). Synchronization and consistency across the different orchestrators can be achieved via additional payload in the service definition and pre-flight checks.

4.1.1.1. NFV Privacy Aware Onboarding Specification

Privacy modelling is formalized within the data management through a systematic method, quantifying service privacy levels using a declarative, service-specific privacy manifest.

The privacy manifest, a statement outlining privacy service definitions, undergoes analysis by a privacy quantification model that employs predefined metrics and algorithms to assess the service's privacy level. This quantification can be customized according to user preferences or regulatory standards, and it is crucial for distinguishing between similar services or enabling benchmarking. The privacy manifest assumes the structure in *Table 2*:

Field	Description
version	The version number of the configuration file (YAML).
provider	The name of the entity providing the data service.

Table 2. Privacy manifest structure.

The quantification result is an analysis executed over the application and/or its description and provides a privacy related score. Depending on the application, and the developer's approach, two sources are considered for this score: developer provided information, and automatically assessed information. The first results from the developer specifically stating the data processing characteristics of the application, including which data is processed, which data is stored and how, and which data is communicated with specific external endpoints. These endpoints relate to external services on a Service Cloud. The second method relies on tools that estimate how data is processed/stored and which is the connectivity graph with external endpoints. As stated, both methods result in a quantification and composite score.

Additionally, the proposed architecture accommodates service updates. It establishes a control version to maintain a privacy benchmark as the service evolves. The privacy quantification component is utilized to re-evaluate the privacy level of the updated service, thereby updating the final metric.

This approach establishes a continuous cycle of privacy testing and monitoring (DevPrivOps). Privacy quantification and re-quantification ensure ongoing assessment and refinement of the service's privacy practices. This iterative approach promotes continual enhancement of privacy practices, aligning the service with evolving privacy standards and best practices.

The requirements associated with privacy quantification are listed in *Table 3*.

ID	Requirement Description	Requirement Type
RIG_FUN_T31_010	The framework should support the traceability, storage, and management of security/privacy policies, as well as the translation from policy models to specific domain element configurations.	Functional requirement
RIG_FUN_T3.3_050	The Trust evaluation and enabler service function shall analyse and determine if there exists any attack trace in the collected data and provide trust data that includes cause code, configuration issues, malfunction alerts, trust value(s), recommended actions, and timestamp.	Functional requirement
RIG_FUN_T41_100	The RIGOUROUS framework should allow users to create the privacy policies and to make configurations using a graphical user interface	Functional requirement
RIG_FUN_T4.3_240	The Threat Risk Assessor shall perform threat risk analytics in accordance with the ZSM General Security Aspects	Functional requirement

Table 3. Requirements associated to privacy quantification.

4.2. Policy-based security network management

The emerging 5G infrastructures are marked by the dynamic deployment of diverse devices, functions, and applications that require continuous configuration, security, and management. The traditional approach to management, where a system administrator handles each individual configuration, is no longer sufficient. Policy-based approaches excel at defining a standardized way to represent various types of requirements, offering a level of abstraction that standardizes management and enables consistency checks.

Over the years, different policy designs and specifications have emerged, focusing on various aspects. However, only a few of them address a broad range of security considerations. To streamline security management, automation, deployment, and configurations across different domains, RIGOUROUS expands upon the multi-level abstraction approach and capabilities

introduced in ANASTACIA-H2020 and INSPIRE-5GPlus projects. Specifically, it will be extended to provide or implement new functionalities such as Network slicing and Federated Learning Monitoring.

In order to better understand the developed policies, they are discussed below in detail. First of all, the High-level Security Policy Language for Orchestration Policies (HSPL-OP) represents high-level security needs, priorities, and interdependencies through high-level orchestration security policies. These policies are detached from specific technologies, encapsulating statements like "Bob can access Internet traffic only after successful authentication." HSPL-OP employs an XML-based framework to articulate security requirements. Below, the Medium-level Security Policy Language for Orchestration Policies (MSPL-OP) enables the modelling of more technical details within medium-level orchestration security policies. While these policies are somewhat less abstract, they remain decoupled from the underlying infrastructure. Consequently, they can represent specific information such as IP addresses or protocols without defining the precise configurations for individual endpoints. Similar to HSPL-OP, MSPL-OP defines priorities and dependencies to enhance orchestration capabilities.

Rigorous requirements linked to the Policy based security management are indicated in *Table 4*.

ID	Requirement description	Functional components
RIG_FUN_T31_010	The framework should support the traceability, storage, and management of security/privacy policies, as well as the translation from policy models to specific domain element configurations.	ISM
RIG_FUN_T31_020	The Intent-Based Security Management component should support different security policies and be able to detect conflicts among policies.	ISM
RIG_DCC_T31_050	The RIGOROUS framework security policy models should be extensible and interoperable.	ISM

Table 4. Policy-based security management requirements.

4.2.1. Policy translation process

Policy orchestration models facilitate the expression of high-level policies using the High-Level Specification Language (HSPL). These high-level policies are then translated into lower-level specifications using the Medium-level Security Policy Language (MSPL), which contains the technical details required for deploying necessary elements, enforcing policies, and ensuring compliance.

The Security Orchestrator comprehends MSPL and actively manages policies across various Security Management Domains. Over time, it may request the translation of MSPL into other formalisms.

In contrast to the refinement process, which can be conducted at both the End-to-End Security Management Domain (E2E SMD) level and the SMD level to refine high-level policies into medium-level policies, the policy translation process takes place exclusively at the SMD level. Its purpose is to translate MSPL-OP into specific infrastructure configurations as part of the SMD orchestration. This process occurs once the SMD Security Orchestrator has identified the appropriate assets for enforcing the MSPL-OP.

Here is how the process unfolds: The SMD Policy Framework receives an MSPL-OP and a list of assets capable of enforcing each MSPL. Subsequently, the Policy Framework initiates the translation process. It dynamically loads a translator plugin for each tuple <MSPL, selected asset> and executes it to obtain all the necessary low-level configurations.

The plugin-based approach offers scalability and an accessible means of incorporating new assets into the policy-based system. Implementing a well-defined method in an isolated piece of code, to be dynamically loaded, is all that is required to introduce new assets. Each plugin is responsible for implementing the logic necessary to translate the MSPL into its final configurations. It also utilizes libraries provided by the policy framework, such as access management to data services, to retrieve essential information about the infrastructure needed for the translation process.

Figure 6 illustrates an instance of translating from MSPL-OP to I2NSF (Interface to Network Security Functions) controller IPsec configurations. In this scenario, the plugin constructs a framework for the IETF IPsec model, which can furnish channel protection information for the IPsec Security Association Database (SAD) and the Security Policy Database (SPD). The process involves parsing the MSPL-OP to extract the necessary values. In cases where values are missing or defaults are needed, data services are utilized to retrieve the required information, and to finalize the translation.

4.2.1.1. Policy models

Filtering Policy

The MSPL filtering policy models are designed to depict configurations related to networking information. *Figure 4* illustrates the expansion of the base configuration condition, enabling the establishment of specific networking parameters such as *packetFilterCondition*, *statefulCondition*, *timeCondition*, *applicationLayerCondition*, *qosCondition*, *aggregatorParameters* and *networkSlicingConditionParameters*.

```
<complexType name="FilteringConfigurationCondition">
  <complexContent>
    <extension base="ITResource:ConfigurationCondition">
      <sequence>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="packetFilterCondition"
          type="ITResource:PacketFilterCondition"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="statefulCondition"
          type="ITResource:StatefulCondition"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="timeCondition"
          type="ITResource:TimeCondition"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="applicationLayerCondition"
          type="ITResource:ApplicationLayerCondition"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="aggregatorParameters"
          type="ITResource:AggregatorParameters"/>
        <!-- ANASTACIA QoS -->
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="qosCondition"
          type="ITResource:QoSCondition"/>
        <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="networkSlicingConditionParameters"
          type="ITResource:NetworkSlicingConditionParameters"/>
      </sequence>
    </extension>
  </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

Figure 4. Expansion of the base configuration condition.

Figure 5 depicts the fields associated with *PacketFilterCondition*. These fields encompass source address, destination address, source and destination ports, source, and destination MAC the direction of connection establishment, the interface, and the protocol type among other.

```
<complexType name="PacketFilterCondition">
  <sequence>
    <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="SourceMAC" type="string"/>
    <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="DestinationMAC" type="string"/>
    <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="SourceAddress" type="string"/>
    <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="DestinationAddress" type="string"/>
    <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="SourcePort" type="string"/>
    <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="DestinationPort" type="string"/>
    <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="direction" type="string"/>
    <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="interface" type="string"/>
    <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="ProtocolType" type="string"/>
    <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="encapsulationType" type="string"/>
    <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="encapsulationID" type="string"/>
    <element name="State" type="string" maxOccurs="unbounded" minOccurs="0"/>
    <element name="bidirectional" type="boolean" maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0"/>
    <element name="encapsulation" type="boolean" maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0"/>
    <element maxOccurs="1" minOccurs="0" name="innerPacket" type="ITResource:PacketFilterCondition"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
```

Figure 5. Fields associated with *PacketFilterCondition*.

The filtering policy plays a fundamental role in the configuration and management of the network, covering devices such as switches, routers, firewalls and SDN controllers, among other components. This policy is responsible for establishing rules that regulate the behaviour of data traffic on the network, thus enabling effective management of information flows.

In detail, the rules defined by the filtering policy address various actions, such as redirection and discarding of data flows within the network. For example, rules can be established to redirect specific types of traffic to particular destinations, which is crucial for optimising network performance and efficiency. At the same time, the ability to discard data flows according to predefined criteria is essential for network security, allowing to block unauthorised access, mitigate threats and maintain system integrity.

In addition, filtering policy plays an essential role in the implementation of security measures, as it can configure specific rules on devices such as firewalls to control what type of traffic is allowed or blocked, thus helping to protect against potential vulnerabilities and attacks.

Channel protection Policy model and translation

Figure 6. IPsec MSPL-OP to I2NSF-IPSec translation.

Channel Protection refers to the implementation of policies and measures aimed at ensuring the integrity, confidentiality and availability of the communication channels used in a network. This involves ensuring that the transmitted information is not altered during its transport (channel integrity), protecting it against unauthorised access (channel confidentiality), and ensuring that the channel is always accessible and functional (channel availability). In addition, authentication and authorisation of the parties involved in the communication, continuous monitoring for anomaly detection, and documentation of compliance with policies are crucial elements in the effective protection of communication channels.

Network Slicing policy model

To model the network slicing policy, the schema that validates XML policies has been extended. First of all, a "ConfigurationRuleAction" is added to define the CREATE and ATTACH actions. In addition, it creates a condition in "ConfigurationCondition", called "NetworkSlicingCondition", in it is contemplated firstly "QoSCondition", this has values like the priority and the maximum and minimum bandwidth. On the other hand, there are the packet filtering conditions "PacketFilterCondition", this contains among other fields the source address or the encapsulation ID, inside "packetFilterCondition" there is the peculiarity of admitting up to "n" encapsulations of the type "packetFilterCondition". Figure 7 and Figure 8 show the transitions through the translations of these policies.

Figure 7. Network Slicing plugin: transition for slice creation.

This translation generates a JSON output for the creation of a new network slice. This output contemplates the "sliceName", "maxBandWidth", "minBandWidth", priority and the "dpid" of the involved host. The dpid contains the host and the port used to find out the route.

To create a new network slicing attachment, as shown in this example, a nesting is used so that the different encapsulations can be contemplated. As can be seen, within each encapsulation the following, among others, are supported the "srcIP", "dstIP", "protocolType", "SourcePort", "DestinationPort", "EncapsulationType" and "encapsulationID".

Figure 8. Network Slicing plugin: transition for attaching slice.

Federated Learning Policy model

To implement and set up the necessary components for Federated Learning (FL) within the infrastructure as Security Agents, an interoperable and innovative FL policy model was developed that encompasses all the essential information. For this purpose, the MSPL-OP was extended, which offers various security capabilities, incorporates concepts from I2NSF IETF, is easily expandable, and has been utilized in significant and related projects like ANASTACIA or INSPIRE-5Gplus. Figure 9 illustrates the newly proposed data model elements designed to guide the FL policy intents. This model will be employed for deploying an FL agent or an FL aggregator. The colours assigned to the boxes in the diagram indicate whether a class is simple, meaning it directly contains the value (lighter colours), or complex (darker colours), meaning it contains other classes, either simple or complex. The numbering on each connection indicate the cardinality, i.e., "0..1" indicates that the connection is optional, while "1" indicates it is mandatory.

As illustrated in Figure 9, there are two higher-level classes, namely "ITResourceOrchestration" and "ITResource", signifying the deployment and configuration of a resource within the infrastructure. In addition to an FL Agent and FL Aggregator, a resource could be another security entity, such as a monitoring probe. In the context of the FL scenario, the "ITResource" is represented as a "FederatedLearningRuleAction", containing the essential information for deploying either an FL Agent or an FL Aggregator. Within this class, there are distinct blocks, such as "AggregatorParameters", containing necessary details for deploying an aggregator (URL, FL rounds, and fusion algorithm to be used), and Agent, which requires knowledge of the aggregator's location but not the rounds or the fusion algorithm.

Furthermore, there are blocks indicating Integration Fabric parameters (“*IntegrationFabricParameters*”), assumed to function as a publish/subscribe platform in this example, where information is stored and retrieved from topics. There are also blocks specifying the details of the ML model to be trained, part of the “*LearningModelInfo*” class. In the case of a Deep Autoencoder for anomaly detection, attributes like “unsupervised” in “*LearningType*”, “neural network” in Type, and “autoencoder” in Subtype should be set. The *AdditionalParameters* attribute can be utilized to provide more details about the model, such as the number of layers, the number of neurons in each layer, or the loss function to be used.

Subsequently, specific parameters for local learning, including the test size, local epochs, steps per epoch, and batch size, can be configured within “*LearningParameters*”. Additionally, mechanisms for obfuscating model updates to prevent membership inference attacks can be established within “*ObfuscationInfo*”. For example, configuring “differential-privacy” in Technique, “Laplace Bounded Domain” in Mechanism, and specifying epsilon and delta values within “*AdditionalParameters*”.

Finally, the “*InstanceThreshold*” attribute denotes the threshold for the number of traffic samples, such as traffic flows, that must be attained to register with the aggregator and initiate federated training.

Figure 9. Federated Learning policy model for Network Intelligence management.

To model federated learning policies, the schema that validates policy XML has been extended. To start with, in “*configureRuleAction*” the actions AGENT, AGGREGATOR and DETECTION are added. A condition is also created in “*configurationCondition*” called “*FLConfigurationCondition*”. Within this, other sections of “*ConfigurationCondition*” are created, these are: “*AgregatorParameters*”, “*IntegrationFabricParameters*”, “*learningModelInfo*”, “*LearningParameters*”, “*obfuscationInfo*”.

The following figures show the translation that the plugin is generating as output of each configuration.

Figure 10. Federated Learning plugin: transition to config agent.

Figure 10 shows the translation of an agent in federated learning. This agent extracts the configuration parameters from the policy and formats them into a configuration output.

Figure 11. Federated Learning plugin: transition to config aggregator.

Figure 11 shows the translation of an aggregator by taking the configuration values passed in the policy and formatting them into a readable structure.

Finally, there is the detection engine translation which behaves like the previous translations.

Figure 12. Federated Learning plugin: transition to config detection engine.

5 AI-DRIVEN CROSS-DOMAIN SECURITY AND PRIVACY ORCHESTRATION IN IOT-EDGE-CLOUD CONTINUUM: FIRST ITERATION

5.1. Security Orchestration

The UMU security orchestrator implemented in the H2020 “INSPIRE-5Gplus” project will be leveraged in RIGOUROUS to make it driven by AI with decision making delivered across all layers of abstraction. AI-based algorithms will run fully deployed across domains and cross network-segments IoT-RAN-EDGE-Core-Cloud in the 6G network, following a Federated Learning (FL) approach to make orchestration decisions. Federated learning will be run in several execution units deployed in device-edge-cloud-continuum to improve the security orchestration capabilities to empower dynamic provisioning, deployment, and reconfiguration (during operation) of the virtual network security functions and associated intents and policies.

The 5G architecture relies on the assembly of modular systems and services that need to be both mission-aware and security-aware. To achieve this, security orchestration is essential to meet expectations, comply with policies, and adhere to regulations.

Security policy orchestration presents several challenges. One challenge pertains to defining the policies themselves. It is crucial to determine how these policies is declared and how compliant resources and services can be computed while complying with policy constraints. Another challenge is related to deploying security enforcement strategies, which involves scheduling and ensuring the availability of security functions and associated resources. Additionally, achieving interoperability and coordinating various authority perimeters is necessary to ensure global security. On the other hand, the flexibility provided by orchestration is expected to greatly benefit the deployment of intelligent protection, detection, and remediation strategies.

Policy-based security orchestration enables the orchestration of security requirements based on clearly defined security policies. This approach facilitates the management of security in intricate and diverse 5G infrastructures by standardizing the final configurations within security policies that offers multiple levels of abstraction. Furthermore, a well-defined policy-based approach notably enhances system consistency by employing various conflict detection and dependency processes.

Figure 13 illustrates the primary workflow for End-to-End (E2E) Orchestration, encompassing both inter and intra-domain orchestration. When the E2E orchestrator receives a High-level Security Policy Language Orchestration Policy (HSPL-OP) (1), an initial high-level conflict detection process is initiated to check for any E2E level issues (2). If the high-level policies within the HSPL-OP do not result in conflicts, the E2E orchestrator identifies the required capabilities with assistance from the Intent-based Security Management (ISM) (3). Simultaneously, it determines the involved domains with support from data services (4). Once the involved domains are identified, the E2E orchestrator retrieves endpoint information for each domain (5). In cases where the capability necessitates common parameters, the E2E orchestrator requests the available parameters for each involved domain (6) and seeks a common solution (7). If a common solution is found, the E2E Orchestrator solicits a customized refinement of the HSPL-OP to the ISM (8). This refinement

process generates Medium-level Security Policy Language Orchestration Policies (MSPL-OP) from the HSPL Orchestration (9), as detailed in Section 2.2. Depending on the specific implementation, some steps of the E2E policy refinement, a part of the E2E Orchestration process, may be delegated to the policy refiner within the ISM to alleviate the E2E Security Orchestrator's workload. Once the E2E Security Orchestrator receives the MSPL-OP, it orchestrates an enforcement plan. In doing so, it identifies the enforcement domain for each security policy, recognizing that it may differ from the targeted domain. The plan is then organized according to the priorities of the security policies, with the management of dependencies, if any (10). Policies with unresolved dependencies are queued until the appropriate event triggers enforcement, while those prepared for enforcement are incorporated into the plan, ordered based on their defined priorities. Finally, the E2E Security Orchestrator instructs the enforcement of policies to the various Management Domains according to the enforcement plan.

Table 5 shows the functional requirements identified and associated with the Security Orchestration.

ID	Requirement description
RIG_FUN_T32_030	The AI-Driven Security Orchestrator should be driven by interoperable intents or policy models.

Table 5. RIGOROUS requirements related to orchestration.

5.1.1. Orchestration Flow

When a Management Domain Security Orchestrator receives a request for MSPL-OP enforcement (11), it conducts an assessment to ensure that the new policies will not create conflicts within the existing domain policies and infrastructure (12). If no conflicts are detected, the Security Orchestrator proceeds with the enforcement of the MSPL-OP (13). This involves determining the most appropriate asset to execute the execution resulting in the translation (14).

To achieve this, an orchestration algorithm retrieves the available candidate assets (15) from the (ISM) and initiates an allocation optimization process. This process selects a suitable policy enforcement point based on several factors, including the available asset plugin, security policy details, data services information, and the chosen allocation algorithm. The selection of the allocation algorithm is critical, as different scenarios may require different approaches. For example, environments lacking NFV-MANO features or with limitations on new deployments may opt for an algorithm that focuses on enforcing policies (16) in the most suitable allocation place among the already deployed or existing assets. Conversely, if the infrastructure supports dynamic deployments, advanced optimization algorithms like weight-based, scored, greedy, Mixed-Integer Linear Programming, ant colony-based, or deep-learning-assisted methods can be employed.

It's worth noting that throughout the orchestration process, multiple conflict verifications are carried out to ensure that the chosen security enablers and allocation resources fully comply with the security policy requirements.

Figure 13. Sequence diagram for primary workflow for End-to-End (E2E) Orchestration.

Mitigation policies in either High-level (HSPL format) or Medium-level (MSPL format) will be transmitted to the system via the "nSO_SecPolEnforc" interface from the AI-driven Decision Engine.

Upon receiving input data, the Security Orchestrator (SO) must establish communication with various functional blocks as shown in Figure 14. These include the Information Security Manager (ISM) for conflict detection, which uses the "nISM_DetConf" interface, and for policy translation purposes, the SO interfaces with "nISM_TransHSPL" or "nISM_TransMSPL". The SO also collaborates with NFV Mano to deploy dedicated Security Agents via the "nNM_DepNFV" interface and configure or reconfigure them post-deployment using "nSA_SecLocEnforc", all driven by predefined policies. Additionally, the SO interacts with the Zero Trust Identity Management ("Ntesf_TrustEvaluation") to acquire trust score information, which is incorporated into the

orchestration algorithm. Lastly, it engages with the Slice Manager to define end-to-end security slices with specific parameters, such as establishing a honeynet for mitigation.

Figure 14. Interaction between WP3 RIGOUROUS functional blocks.

5.1.2. Conflict and Dependency detection

This section addresses the potential risks associated with conflicts that may arise between inconsistent platform and service provisioning, and security functions. In today's networks, complexity and diversity have reached unprecedented levels. In the 5G era, the interconnection of thousands of devices from various technologies demands an automatic and optimized response to events, along with the adaptability to system and device capabilities to ensure the proper behaviour of authorized devices. In response to this challenge, Inspire5G introduces a policy-based framework designed to harness the maximum potential of Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV). Within this framework, the 5G infrastructure, equipped with a well-defined policy procedure, exhibits self-healing and self-repair capabilities. It is adept at detecting and mitigating potential inconsistencies within the system. These policies serve as an abstraction layer that simplifies underlying complexities and facilitates the definition of rules that must be adhered to by the system to ensure intended behaviour.

Before the enforcement of new security policies in the system, it is imperative to identify any potential incompatibilities, contradictions, or dependencies with the current infrastructure's state. To address this need, the INSPIRE-5GPlus Policy Framework's security enabler incorporates the Policy Conflict Detector module, an extension of previous approaches [2] designed to handle conflicts at both the End-to-End (E2E) Management Domain level and the Management Domain level. This module incorporates a rule engine that assesses the requested security policies against a set of rules and a knowledge base (facts). Organizations can build upon a well-established set of rules, customizing and expanding them to detect specific conflicts and dependencies. Moreover, new rules can be dynamically added as part of reactive processes.

The following snippet provides an example of a rule (duties conflict). These logical rules consist of an antecedent representing rule conditions and a consequent that is executed when the antecedent conditions are met. Therefore, the consequent is only triggered when the specified conditions are fulfilled. The rules reference statements from security policies as well as elements provided by data services, such as infrastructure-related information. Furthermore, when a consequent is triggered, it is also considered as a new fact. This feature enables the addition of further facts when specific contextual and policy conditions are satisfied. By following this approach, a set of semantic rules is established to automatically detect inconsistencies and semantic conflicts within the managed system based on facts derived from security policies and data services information. This rule-based reasoning process automates the detection of inconsistencies and conflicts in the managed system.

5.1.3. FL for Anomaly Detection Orchestration

5.1.3.1. FL Orchestration process (proactive)

The orchestration of Federated Learning in a vast, distributed 5G network is a pivotal undertaking that facilitates smooth coordination and collaboration among diverse entities. This process aids in configuring, deploying, and managing Federated Learning features. *Figure 15* illustrates the suggested proactive Federated Learning Orchestration process, engaging multiple Security Management Domains across various levels (Core, Transport, RAN).

The orchestration process can be initiated proactively or reactively, depending on the origin of the request. In the proactive workflow, a user requests the deployment of Federated Learning (FL) features and capabilities across the multidomain infrastructure. The End-to-End (E2E) Security Orchestrator examines the requested capabilities, formulates an orchestration plan to distribute Federated Learning and anomaly detection tasks across underlying domains, and generates the necessary FL security policies. These policies, modelled in the Medium-level Security Policy Language (MSPL) according to the FL model defined in the previous section, are then dispatched to different domains (*Figure 15* steps 1 and 16). The Security Management Domain (SMD) orchestrators receive the MSPL-OP policy, comprising FL Agent policies and one FL Aggregator policy, and gather information on available security enablers—software or hardware components capable of implementing the required capabilities, FL Agent, and FL Aggregation (*Figure 15* step 2). Once the Security Orchestrator has a list of enabler candidates, it executes the allocation algorithm to select the most suitable candidate and deployment location for the FL Agents and the FL Aggregator, considering the context, environment, and constraints (*Figure 15* step 3). To enforce the deployment, the Security Orchestrator leverages the NFV-MANO component to deploy the agents and the aggregator in the designated location (*Figure 15* steps 4, 5, and 6).

In the subsequent phase, the Security Orchestrator configures the enablers, comprising FL Agents and FL Aggregator, with the specified parameters (*Figure 15* steps 7 and 8). Agents initiate registration with the aggregator upon reaching the instance threshold. Collaborating with these registered agents, the aggregator generates a new global model over the specified number of training rounds outlined in the aggregator configuration policy (*Figure 15*, steps 9 and 10).

Figure 15. FL Orchestration Process, proactive workflow.

Upon completion of the final model, the FL Aggregator informs the monitoring module (Figure 15 step 11), triggering the Decision Engine (Figure 15 step 12). The Decision Engine generates a new MSPL policy, designating FL Detection as the primary capability, along with the latest model provided by the FL Aggregator (Figure 15 step 13). Subsequently, the Security Orchestrator receives the request and initiates the orchestration process, culminating in the deployment of the AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine based on the trained model (Figure 15 steps 14 and 15).

5.1.3.2. FL Orchestration process (reactive)

Upon detecting anomalies, the framework is equipped to execute real-time reactive measures to implement appropriate countermeasures. When an anomaly is identified by the AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine, it notifies the Decision Engine, which devises a set of mitigation policies to be orchestrated and enforced for mitigating the attack. In this reactive phase, the Decision Engine may initiate a new learning process, enabling agents to provide the AI-based Anomaly Detection Engine with a more current model, incorporating the latest network status and monitored data. Additional actions, such as deploying additional FL Agents and AI-based Anomaly Detection Engines throughout the infrastructure to safeguard previously unconsidered domains/subdomains, can also be taken.

It is crucial to emphasize that the reactive stage of the framework extends beyond enhancing FL features to encompass a comprehensive range of countermeasures. The decision module may deduce diverse mitigation actions based on the identified threat. For example, it could generate a filtering policy to intercept malicious traffic as close to the source as possible, request the implementation of a security slice for communication protection, deploy a honeynet, or assign the attacker to a data-plane slice with minimum QoS, among other possibilities.

5.1.3.3. FL-based Anomaly Detection

As outlined in earlier sections, the deployment involves at least one aggregator and multiple agents distributed across domains. Following deployment and configuration, the conventional FL workflow unfolds, where agents individually train models using their local traffic data, and the aggregator, through multiple learning rounds, amalgamates these individual models into a global one.

The proposed model for real-time anomaly detection tasks post-training is a Deep Autoencoder. This model is designed to reconstruct the input into the output. The Autoencoder is trained with flow-based non-anomalous traffic samples extracted from the network. Subsequently, the Autoencoder becomes adept at reconstructing these samples with minimal error. As the error can be dynamically measured, an error threshold can be set to assess new traffic. Traffic flows surpassing the threshold will be classified as anomalies, indicating significant deviations from the non-anomalous traffic dataset the model was trained on.

The orchestrator will initially deploy and configure the necessary FL agents for model generation. Once the initial model is obtained, AI-based Anomaly Detection Engines, equipped with the model, will be deployed and capable of distinguishing between normal and anomalous samples. If an anomaly is detected, it will alert higher-level components through the Integration Fabric, enabling the selection and enforcement of further classification and ultimate mitigation measures across the infrastructure.

5.1.4. Orchestration Algorithms

During the orchestration process, the Security Orchestrator is not configured to always use the same method for deciding the best allocation for a given policy, but it can select from a range of different options the more suitable one depending on a set of parameters or the context. This way, the Security Orchestrator can optimize the orchestration using a MSPL policy and the aforementioned information as inputs, considering different constraints and variables in order to generate the optimal orchestration for all the critical assets (for instance, network latency, CPU use, or disk availability). These assets can be categorized as:

- **Constraint Management:** the SO must consider the restrictions stated in policies while optimizing the orchestration. Some examples are node-specific requirements or user-defined policies.

- **Location Awareness:** the geographic location of the devices that take part in the orchestration can be used to minimize communication costs and respect the data regulations.
- **Resource Allocation:** resources must be allocated and released efficiently, avoiding their misuse.
- **Trade-off Management:** ensure that the user is able to balance trade-offs between different elements, such as power consumption, cost, or performance, and generate orchestration results according to their priorities.
- **Network Latency:** locate workloads near to their sources or endpoints in order to minimize the latency obtaining or sending data.

Before selecting the appropriate algorithm for each situation, the Security Orchestrator must process the MSPL policies, deciding how to solve the problem of optimizing the orchestration following the restrictions. It can use other algorithms to check if the result obtained is able to generate a planning that provides the best result, and to identify the best suitable software to deploy it, which is also performed using optimization algorithms. Methods that might consider solving the optimization problem comprise: ILP, Greedy-based, Simulated Temple, Ant Colony, and IA.

5.2. Bootstrapping and onboarding

IoT device bootstrapping describes how the IoT devices can connect to a network for authentication and secure connection setup. The IoT devices may have different capabilities in terms of operating system, communication technology, supported security algorithms, processing power and battery life. Those devices need to onboard to the 6G network according to their capabilities and needs to get provisioned securely with long term credentials with respect to their supported security algorithms. The provisioning of the long-term credentials needs to be protected from MitM attacks to prevent unauthorized access, impersonation attacks and privilege escalation from the eavesdropper.

Linked non-functional Requirements includes the following:

- RIG_SEC_T3.2_1200: The end-device shall be able to identify and verify trusted applications installed on the device.
- RIG_SEC_T3.2_060: The system shall be able to securely bootstrap the end-devices and onboard them with respective credentials for access authentication/authorization.

The Trusted Application Onboarding describes how to avoid that malicious applications are installed in the IoT devices and take over the resources granted for the genuine applications. If applications on the device are privileged by the network operator e.g., in terms of QoS, slice access, throughput, charging, etc., then the application needs to be uniquely identified by the UE/IoT device. Mobile operators have the possibility to manage those applications with UE Route Selection Policy (URSP) rules, where an application is identified with an application identifier and

the corresponding operating system identifier within the traffic descriptor component of an URSP rule. The application identity is used in the UE to map the data connection with specific data connection parameters.

Since the application identity can be set during the development of the application, and is non-protected, it is not suitable to uniquely identify the traffic of the application, intended to be managed by the operator. The user may install an application on the UE with the same application identity to transmit the traffic based on the URSP rule, which was designed to be applied for the traffic of the genuine application.

Linked Requirement:

- RIG_SEC_T3.2_650: The end-device shall be able to identify and verify trusted applications installed on the device.

5.2.1. Component Design

5.2.1.1. Zero-Touch Device Bootstrapping

Figure 16. IoT Bootstrapping and device onboarding.

Figure 16 shows the bootstrapping and onboarding of the IoT devices (UEs), the devices first connect to the onboarding network, gets authenticated, and authorized for long term credential provisioning. The IoT devices may be preconfigured with onboarding credentials for a protected and secured connection with a credential holder, who authenticates the IoT device during the

onboarding process and selects the corresponding provisioning server with the long-term credentials based on the subscription and the device capabilities. Then the Provisioning Server selects and provisions the long-term credentials for authentication/authorization with the network for normal operations. The IoT devices from now on connect only to the network for normal operations, using the provisioned long-term credentials for authentication/authorization and protection of the communication and signalling. The onboarding network may be the same network as the network for normal operations.

5.2.1.2. Trusted Application Onboarding

Devices may be able to install applications from different sources, where intentional or by accident also malicious applications could be installed on the device. Especially, if applications are managed by the network operator and granted certain privileges in terms of network slice access, charging, QoS etc., then a malicious application could hijack those privileges, if the genuine applications are not uniquely identified.

For this reason, the network shall provide additional identification information to the UE in the URSP rule so that the UE can enforce the URSP rule correctly only for the trusted applications as illustrated in *Figure 17*.

Figure 17. Application Identification Information Provisioning.

A typical application package consists of the original application, a digital certificate of the application developer and a digital signature of the original application. The UE verifies the signature based on the embedded certificate and only if the verification is successful, the UE can install the application. In order to assure that the correct application is installed and not a non-genuine one, additional information from the application package, which is available in the UE and in the application store, shall be used for the URSP rule enforcement in the UE and to identify a non-genuine application with a genuine application identity, since the certificate of a non-genuine application developer is different to the one of the genuine application developer.

Every UE application is signed with a unique digital certificate, which typically contains a validity period, the publisher of the application, the public key of the publisher, etc. Before the application is published (e.g. to a mobile marketplace), it is cryptographically signed by using the private key of the publisher, which is a unique key only known by the publisher. An example of an application signing procedure is shown in *Figure 18*. The generated digital signature and the digital certificate that can be used to validate the authenticity of the application, both are included in the application package, which can be published and distributed.

Figure 18. Example of application signing.

A non-genuine application with the same application ID as the genuine application would have a different certificate, since the developer of the non-genuine application does not have access to the private key of the genuine application publisher. Therefore, the URSP rule is enhanced to include a fingerprint (hash) of the genuine publisher certificate as additional information so that the UE can easily compare it with the fingerprint of the certificate of the application which is installed on the UE.

5.2.2. Privacy-preserving ABC Verifiable credentials enrolment

Digital credentials give users control over authentication procedures, not having to rely on a third party for performing authentication processes. However, plain credentials are lacking in terms of privacy: credentials are linkable, which leads to user tracking, and desirable properties like minimal disclosure are not practically feasible. In this sense, privacy-preserving Attribute-Based Credentials, or anonymous credentials (p-ABC), which enable potential privacy features like minimal disclosure and unlinkability, while enabling trustworthy certification of attributes.

More specifically, ABCs are digital credentials that serve as a mean to prove a user's identity or his possession of some attributes (properties, roles...) to another party. They are based on the trust of the verifying party in the authority that issues the credentials. A common real-world example could be a person's national identity document, which he may use to prove being older than eighteen to a vendor to buy alcohol. Apart from illustrating the idea behind ABCs, this example shows a potential problem they present by examining the DNI (Document National Identifier), the vendor would not only learn the attribute that needed to be proven but all attributes within the credential like full name or nationality.

In contrast, the concept of privacy-preserving ABC (p-ABC) was introduced by Chaum [3]. The idea behind p-ABCs is that, once a user has received a credential from an issuer where his attributes are verified, he can use it to derive proofs (e.g., called presentation tokens) which may not include all the information contained in the credential. Then, the other party (relying party or service provider) can verify that the data revealed in the presentation token comes from a valid credential issued by the trusted issuer (which may contain more attributes that remain hidden).

A p-ABC scheme will provide the following properties. Unforgeability, so that it is not possible to forge credentials when not possessing the issuing key, nor to forge presentation tokens that would be accepted by the relying party if a user does not possess a valid credential that fulfils the requirements. Minimal disclosure and unlikability, so that presentation tokens reveal only the necessary information for a specific purpose, without leakage of information, including whether two presentation tokens belong to the same or different users, even if multiple verifiers (or issuers) collude.

p-ABC schemes can be extended with additional features. One of them is what could be called selective linkability. There are situations where controlled linkability of presentation tokens can be desirable, like a service maintaining some kind of state information per user so it can offer a personalized experience. This could be accomplished by the use of pseudonyms, of which a user can use several that are unlinkable. Another appealing feature could be the possibility of invalidating a credential, habitually called revocation, or allowing a trustworthy third party to re-identify users, improving security while not reducing privacy capabilities against relying parties. Therefore, envisioned 6G networks can benefit from p-ABC models, as any kind of UE devices, e.g. IoT devices or mobile terminals, can enrol on the 6G network and get an p-ABC during the issuance process, that can be used afterwards to access to network and application services in 6G. This is specifically relevant in untrusted visiting subdomains and networks that a UEs might visit during handover or roaming, where confidentiality and privacy aspects are crucial. In this sense, UEs can derive privacy-preserving proofs of knowledge of certain identity attributes they hold in their p-ABC, that might be needed to access to the 6G services, thereby ensuring privacy-preserving model.

This p-ABC model and in particular the credential Issuance process for identity enrolment fits properly in the device bootstrapping introduced above, as the authentication in the 6G performed for long-term credential provisioning can be instantiated for these kinds of p-ABC credentials. Thus, the Provisioning server explained previously can represent the p-ABC Issuer server.

As described before, the main advantage of p-ABCs is that they conform to a user-centric approach, giving the user control over his online identity. With them, users can control which information about them is revealed to other parties and can, in general, protect their privacy in online exchanges. However, p-ABCs present some disadvantages too. To use a p-ABC scheme, users have to manage their credentials. Stolen credentials would reveal private information to an attacker and could be used to impersonate the user. This forces users to use some kind of secure storage (be it hardware or software based), use hardware-bound credentials.

Moreover, handling p-ABCs is more complex (in general) than traditional identification systems, which are based on standard cryptography methods like widely used signature schemes. For p-ABCs, credentials rely on an issuer's signature over the user attributes, and Zero Knowledge (ZK) proofs are needed for deriving presentation tokens. No standard implementations of such schemes exist, so users and verifiers would have to rely on custom software, which makes more difficult the wide adoption of p-ABCs. Lastly, they are more computationally expensive than schemes based on traditional signatures.

Additionally, just relying on p-ABCs may not be enough to ensure user's privacy. Namely, as it happens in similar privacy-enhancing tools, unlinkability can be jeopardized through two avenues.

First, users may choose to reveal identifying information, like a unique id (e.g., passport number). Second, fingerprinting techniques that rely on data outside the authentication mechanism itself (IP, web-tracking techniques) could be leveraged to link different processes to the same user. In the former case, with p-ABCs, users will know and control which identity information they are sharing, so they must carefully decide which service providers they are willing to access depending on that. In the latter, other complementary privacy-enhancing tools can be applied, like anonymous communication systems or privacy-aware browsers.

5.2.3. Primary Workflows

5.2.3.1. Device Bootstrapping Call Flow

The device bootstrapping process is shown in the sequence diagram in *Figure 19*. The UE is identified by the Default Credentials Server (DCS) based on the onboarding Subscription Concealed Identifier (SUCI), the DCS can de-conceal the SUCI to an onboarding SUPI. The DCS can authenticate the UE based on the onboarding credentials and provision the Master Session Key (MSK) to the Authentication Server Function (AUSF) for setting up the security over the radio interface for Access Stratum (AS) and Non-Access Stratum (NAS) per normal procedures. The DCS and UE derive a provisioning key which is used to protect the profile from the Provisioning Server.

1. The UE sends a Registration Request with the Onboarding SUCI of the DCS as UE identity to the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF).
2. The AMF detects based on the realm of the Network Access Identifier (NAI) that the Registration Request is not from a subscriber of the Network but for onboarding at a DCS. The AMF authorizes the request by verifying the realm of the NAI and whether the Network has an active agreement with this DCS. The AMF forwards the request to the AUSF which may be preconfigured for handling requests towards external DCS.
3. The AUSF may perform authorization of the registration request by verifying the realm of the NAI and whether the Network has an active agreement with this DCS. The AUSF identifies the DCS and takes the role of an Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting (AAA)-Proxy, sending a related AAA message to the corresponding AAA-Server. The AUSF sends an Authentication Request with the onboarding SUCI to the DCS. The Service Based Interface (SBI)-DIAMETER interworking functionality is collocated with the AUSF.
4. The DCS de-conceals the SUCI to a Subscription Permanent Identifier (SUPI) and verifies the authentication request based on the username. The DCS selects the subscriber profile based on the SUPI and performs an Extensible Authentication Protocol (EAP) based authentication with the UE, using the pre-shared onboarding credentials in the UE and in the DCS.
5. After successful authentication, the DCS sends the result of the authentication, the onboarding SUPI, MSK, validity time and address of the Provisioning Server back in an authentication response to the AUSF.

Figure 19. Sequence diagram for IoT device bootstrapping.

6. The AUSF verifies the response and derives the K_{AUSF} from the MSK and the K_{SEAF} according to 3GPP TS 33.501. the UE is performing the same key derivation accordingly.
7. The AUSF sends an authentication response to the AMF/SEAF including the authentication result from the DCS and the K_{SEAF} , the onboarding SUPI, the validity time, i.e. time until the onboarding expires and the address of the Provisioning Server.
8. The AMF performs NAS SMC with the UE.
9. After a successful NAS SMC procedure, the AMF sends the Registration Accept including the address of the Provisioning Server.
10. The UE performs a normal PDU Session Establishment procedure to gain IP connectivity.
11. The UE and the DCS derive a Provisioning Key (K_{Pro}) from the MSK in the same way.
12. The DCS provides the provisioning information Onboarding SUPI and Provisioning Key K_{Pro} the Provisioning Server. The selection for the Provisioning Server may be performed based on the stored address in the DCS per onboarding SUPI.
13. The Provisioning Server selects the Profile based on the onboarding SUPI.
14. The UE establishes and IPsec SA with the Provisioning Server by using the K_{Pro} . All messages are now confidentiality and integrity protected by the IPsec tunnel.
15. The Provisioning Server provisions the new profile to the UE via the IPsec tunnel.
16. The Provisioning Server acknowledges the successful provisioning to the DCS.
17. The DCS deletes or deactivates the onboarding profile that relates to the onboarding SUPI. This prevents that if onboarding credentials are compromised, succeeding impersonation attacks from malicious UEs are prevented from being provisioned with the valid profile.
18. The UE deregisters from the Onboarding network and may also delete or deactivate the onboarding profile.
19. The UE select the Network according to the provisioned profile and registers to the Network according to the normal procedures in TS 23.501/TS 33.501.

5.2.3.2. Trusted Application Onboarding Call Flow

As a precondition, the UE has installed an application with a specific application ID, and it computed the fingerprint of the embedded certificate of the publisher of that application.

Figure 20. URSP rule delivery procedure.

The sequence diagram in *Figure 20* illustrates the URSP rule delivery procedure step by step:

1. The Policy Control Function (PCF) is provisioned with the application ID and additionally with the fingerprint of the certificate of the genuine publisher from an Application Function (AF).
2. If the UE should receive the application specific URSP rule, the PCF will send a URSP rule delivery message with the application ID, certificate fingerprint and routing information etc. to the UE.
3. If the installed application in the UE wants to send data, the UE determines whether the application ID and the publisher certificate fingerprint of the installed application matches with the ones included in the URSP rule. If the match is successful, the UE applies the URSP rule accordingly.

Since every application is signed with the certificate that is included in the application package, the UE will determine whether a certificate is from a genuine publisher or installed from a different developer, even if the application IDs are the same. A non-genuine application cannot include the genuine certificate since the developer of the non-genuine application does not have the private key of the genuine application to sign it. Thus, if the genuine certificate would be included in the non-genuine application package and the signature would be computed with another key, the UE would not install the application because the signature, computed with the public key of the genuine certificate, does not match the one computed by the non-genuine application developer.

5.3. privacy-preserving ABC Verifiable Credentials processes

5.3.1. p-ABC verifiable credential issuance process

The credential issuance process is used by a subject (in this case a UE/IoT device) to obtain a p-ABC verifiable credential. After successful authentication in the 6G network the UE gets a provisioning key that will be used for authentication against the Issuer (a.k.a. Provisioning server).

This authentication against the Issuer can be used (using IKE). The provisioning key can be used also for setting-up an IPsec tunnel between the UE and the Issuer to ensure confidentiality during the credential provisioning. Thus, after the UE authentication, the Default Authentication Server (DCS) redirects the request to the Provisioning Server, (i.e., to the p-ABC Issuer) for direct E2E authentication and p-ABC credential issuance between UE and Issuer. It should be noted that there must be a trusted relationship agreement between both entities that can be materialized through Smart Contracts on Distributed Ledger Technologies. The credential format might follow the verifiable Credentials structure [4]. This credential structure, which defines the attribute structure of the credential, is provided by the Issuer, based on the attributes relevant for network UE identification.

Usually, the process for obtaining the crypto credential between both parties is as follows: once both parties have finished the initialization and they share the same credential definition, and there is secure channel established between Issuer and UE (subject), the issuer starts the p-ABC issuance process with the subject UE, computing a random value called nonce (to prove freshness) that is sent to the subject. Then, the subject computes a cryptographic message (also known as crypto token) according to the credential structure. The issuance message with the token is sent to the issuer, which creates a cryptographic part of the credential signing the attributes with his secret key. It also creates a proof of correctness. Furthermore, the issuer can save the pseudonym and the context for accountability purposes. Finally, the issuer replies to the subject by sending a cryptographic message with the proof of correctness and the attributes signature. The subject verifies this cryptographic material, and based on this message, it generates and stores the credential.

5.3.2. p-ABC verifiable credentials usage

Once the UE holds the p-ABC verifiable credential, it can be used for different purposes such as authenticate itself in untrusted sub-networks or derive proofs of its attributes that might be needed to access to net-apps, 6G services, to authenticate and access directly to other previously unknown devices (as long as they also trust the Issuer) in a D2D interaction. To this aim, the process can benefit from Distributed Ledger technologies improving confidence in the entire infrastructure and reducing the chances of fraud. Thus, entities can rely on DLT to gain insights of the reliability of Issuers, in addition UEs can access information about trusted services that are registered-audited in DLTs. Furthermore, DLT can also increase the reliability trustworthiness between Issuers and target services.

In this case, these entities play the role of Verifier as they require the subject to present a verifiable credential(s) with a certain cryptographic proof and/or verifiable presentation to demonstrate the possession of a certain credential or specific identity attributes. To this aim, the verifier computes a random value called nonce that is sent to the subject. Based on context, the subject can derive proofs of identity or pseudonym to be used against the verifier service. Optionally, in case the subject does know the proof specification that is required by the target accessing service, the verifier can send a presentation policy stating which data must be disclosed by the subject to gain access to the requested service. In other words, the presentation policy

defines which credentials and attributes are required and/or which conditions have to be fulfilled by the attributes. The subject (acting as prover) defines the proof specification from the selected credential(s) to be used against the verifier. This proof includes the nonce and attributes, as well as statements about these attributes. Then, the prover builds a cryptographic object as proof and sends it along with the specification to the verifier. The verifier validates the incoming proof specification using the cryptographic proof. It computes the verifying protocols to check that the attributes statements and pseudonyms are valid. The verifier, depending on the validation result, can send an affirmative or negative response to the subject. Furthermore, the p-ABC system allows the UE to generate pseudonyms that demonstrate the possession of its master secret during the proving protocol explained above, enhancing unlikability. The proof generated by the subject proves to the target the knowledge of the secret associated with a pseudonym, as well as the fact that such a pseudonym is based on the subject's master secret key.

6 ZERO TRUST AND SMART SECURITY MANAGEMENT: FIRST ITERATION

6.1. State of the Art for Trust Evaluation

Trust evaluation and management techniques have been previously used in different studies and projects. For instance, authors in [5] propose the use of different existing security concepts in trust management, such as proof of transit, trust and reputation models, manifests, Security-by-Contract, remote attestation, and root cause analysis, among others. Other studies, like [6], propose using a Service Legal Agreement (SLA) capability framework to determine assurance dimensions while preserving data confidentiality, integrity, and availability, incorporating security capabilities in SLA contexts to provide trust between customer and service provider. Authors of COMMITMENT [7] provide a good example of trust and reputation models, using information from previous fog node interactions (direct and indirect) in fog computing.

About trust data sharing, there are some different schemas aiming to model security information. Structured Threat Information Expression (STIX) [8] is an XML-based language used to exchange cyber threat intelligence, sponsored by MITRE. Other alternative also based in XML is Incident Object Description Exchange Format (IODEF) [9], an IETF standard format used in computer security information representation. Even these models provide a high level of flexibility, most of the mechanisms used to share information using them are not defined, heavy, or difficult to use, thus its adoption is very limited. For this reason, the NIST proposed a mechanism to protect their devices using a threat MUD (Manufacturer Usage Description) [10] file. While a usual MUD file [11] is associated with a device and is used to establish preventive rules (for instance, providing Access Control Lists to identify regular patterns and behaviours), the threat MUD is associated with a threat and is used to establish configuration rules and limit access to the domains. The use of MUD in security has been increased lately, for instance authors in [12] have managed Software Defined Networks (SDNs) translating MUD files into SDN rules, enforced in the SDN switches. In the same way, authors of [13] have applied the same MUD approach to OpenFlow-enabled devices, using Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP) to detect IoT interactions and to install MUD configurations in devices. There are also other examples of MUD use in 5G, such as [14], that provides a description to integrate MUD into 4G/5G core network using Protocol Configuration Options (PCOs) to share Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs) from devices to cellular core network elements, with the possibility to apply additional policies for IoT devices. Nevertheless, these contributions do not provide essential capabilities for 5G ecosystems and are not aligned with ETSI ZSM and are not integrated in a 5G security framework.

The Zero Trust management assumes no implicit trust in the network and continuously analyses and evaluates the risks to the network assets/resources. Some of the primary assets/resources in a communication network includes radio access network entities, core network functions, application functions, data storage/management network functions, operation, and management functions etc. In Zero Trust, the protections usually involve minimizing access to resources (e.g., data and services) to only those subjects and assets requesting access by considering the authentication, authorization, and security posture of the requestor (i.e., including the behavioural statistics, reported threats/attacks etc.,).

Existing authentication methods used in 5G system/5G-advanced system (e.g., TLS used in SBA security and IP sec used for non-SBA security) and Authorization aspects (e.g., OAuth based access tokens) can be reused for the 6G network security, but that is not sufficient. If any network resource/asset is compromised, it can lead to lateral movement of the attack. The existing authentication mechanisms can help to verify identity authentication and authorization can help to enforce access restrictions based on OAuth access token, but none of the existing mechanism helps to identify the risk associated to the compromised network asset/resource, neither prevents any lateral movement of threat.

Further the zero trust and smart security management enables creation of access control security policies based on security evaluation/monitoring results to enforce fine grained access control (e.g., to prevent threat lateral movement). Hence the goal is to design, develop and specify the Trust evaluation and enabler service framework as an extension to the existing 5G system security framework, to ensure security and trustworthiness in the beyond 5G (B5G) and 6G services and communication.

The Trust evaluation and enabler service framework will provide set of functionalities and services (for abnormal behaviour-based security evaluation and monitoring and to use gained insight(s) for security policy generation and fine-grained access control) such as:

- Trust evaluation and enabler service function (TESF) to evaluate the trustworthiness of any target in the network, where a target will be a network node/function in the Core, RAN, end-user device(s) (e.g., UEs), application function etc., and the TESH will provide the trust data notifications to a set of authorized trust service consumers (i.e., network node(s) / function(s) in the core or management domain);
- Trust evaluation and enabler service function(s) can offer subscribe/unsubscribe and notification service for the trust service consumers.
- Event based Direct data collection and Trust evaluation.
- Event based Indirect data collection (via OAM) and Trust evaluation.
- Trust service consumer(s) based on the trust data notifications (e.g., security and trust evaluation results), and locally configured security policies performs invocation of recommended actions to ensure trusted services and service continuation.

The requirements associated with zero trust and smart security management are in *Table 6* shown below.

ID	Requirements Marked in Green in WP 2 Excel Sheet	Associated ZTM Function	Requirement Type
RIG_FUN_T3.3_040	The access control functions (e.g., network repository function) shall enforce access control (i.e., for service consumption and provision) in accordance with the trust-based security policies.	Network Repository Function (NRF)	Functional requirement

RIG_FUN_T3.3_050	The Trust evaluation and enabler service function shall analyse and determine if there exists any attack trace in the collected data and provide trust data that includes cause code, configuration issues, malfunction alerts, trust value(s), recommended actions, and timestamp.	TESF (with the help of AID)	Functional requirement
RIG_FUN_T3.3_060	The Policy control function shall create security policies based on the trust data and notify to the access control functions	PCF	Functional requirement
RIG_FUN_T3.3_070	The system shall perform security monitoring and trust evaluation using one or more Trust evaluation and enabler service function(s)	TESF (with the help of Operator's Security evaluation and Monitoring tools/functions (e.g., SIEM) or SAE/AID/TRA)	Functional requirement
RIG_SEC_T3.3_010	The system shall enable Trust evaluation and enabler service function to collect inference data such as logs and reports that include abnormal event(s) from the devices or network functions, via the management function. An abnormal event can be related to (i) the predefined service message violations, and (ii) the number of received service messages exceeding a configured limit in a time	TESF /Trust evaluation enabler	Non-functional requirement

Table 6. RIGOUROUS requirements associated with zero trust and smart security management.

To this end with the requirements and goals, the Zero Trust Management function offered by the RIGOUROUS Framework proposes event (e.g., abnormal behaviour) based data collection and exposure to enable security risk/threat identification by Operator's security evaluation/monitoring tools and functions.

6.2. Component Design

6.2.1. Trust Evaluation and Enabler Service Function

In this section the Trust Evaluation and Enabler Service Function is defined which is distributed between the Management Domain (termed as TESH_OAM) and the Network Domain (TESF). Further the component design of the Trust evaluation and enabler service framework to achieve the distributed TESH related are described in the following subcategories shown in *Figure 21*.

Figure 21. TESH component Diagram.

The TESH enabler residing in the core network can facilitate data collection from the core NFs (e.g., NRF to get NF load, status related information) and it can collect threat/malicious behaviour related data from the Core NFs (as well as AFs) and RAN node via the TESH management service provider in the management domain (TESF_OAM).

Some of the malicious behaviour related data that need to be collected includes ‘violations of specified normal behaviours’, ‘service requests exceeding configured limits’, ‘critical configuration changes’, etc. The malicious/abnormal behaviour/threat related event in a NF or RAN can happen either due to another misbehaving or compromised NF/RAN/UE, in such a case the related event needs to be logged as a security log/report or inference data at the experiencing NF/RAN node side and it should be collected by the TESH via the OAM’s management services.

The following highlight-level ZTS management integration over the RIGUROUS framework shows that TESH can collect data either directly or indirectly and provides the collected data to the 6G

cyber-Threat Monitoring System (i.e., that can have a Security evaluation and monitoring tool/function (SEMF) e.g., SIEM for instance, this can be equivalent to SAE shown in the RIGOUROUS framework). The 6G cyber-Threat Monitoring System which perform SEMF related function (e.g., SAE) can perform security evaluation and identify if any attack trace exists in the set of data received from the TESH using AI based algorithms implemented for the attack/threat detection. If an attack trace exists, the 6G cyber threat monitoring system can generate the evaluation results and provides the evaluation results (as trust data) to the TESH, where in the evaluation results can include:

- security evaluation information (i.e., output results e.g., if a threat occurred or not, who is the initiator of the threat e.g., an identifier),
- cause (e.g., any attack identified DoS/DDoS/hijack/cyber-attack), and
- time window.

Further the TESH (e.g., which is part of the ZTM in the management domain of RIGOUROUS framework) provides the received trust evaluation data to the Security and Policy Enforcement function to create access control security policies and to enforce fine grained access control (i.e., any network asset/resource (e.g., network function) identified with malicious behaviours should not be allowed to provide service or to consume service. Similarly, any network asset/resource (e.g., RAN node) or UE identified with malicious behaviours should not be allowed to provide service or to consume service. Alternatively, such misbehaving network function can be deprioritized in network function/slice selection to offer any critical service (e.g., URLLC, aerial services for UAVs etc.).

Table 7 shows the target data collection Information:

Information	Source and Operation semantics	Description
NF resource usage	OAM Subscribe/Notification	The usage of assigned virtual resources currently in use for specific NF instance(s) (mean usage of virtual CPU, memory, disk) as defined in clause 5.7 of TS 28.552 [8].
NF resource configuration	OAM Subscribe/Notification	The life cycle changes of specific NF resources (e.g. NF operational or interrupted during virtual/physical resources reconfiguration) as defined in clause 5.2 of TS 28.533 [19].
Violations of specified normal behaviours	OAM Subscribe/Notification	The normal behaviour (of a UE/RAN node/NF) can be considered as baseline to identify any violation to the normal behaviour. The specified message format, input(s)/output(s) are considered as messages related to baseline normal behaviour. E.g., for NFs in core network, the NF service-related service operation, input/output that will be used are specified. So, any violation to this predefined service operation message can be counted as a data to be

		collected from the NF and provided to the TESP by means of management interface.
Service requests exceeding configured limits	OAM Subscribe/Notification	Each RAN node and NF can be configured with maximum allowed threshold to received and process any service request. If the number of service request exceeds the preconfigured limit, then it may be due to flooding attack attempts. So, such violation of preconfigured limits and related service requestor information should be collected.
Critical configuration changes	OAM Subscribe/Notification	Each NF comes with basic configuration such as NF profile, security algorithm to be supported/used, local policy etc. In such as case, if there occurs any attempt to change the configuration by unauthorized means, then such event information can be collected from the NFs and provided. Similar data collection aspect can also be applied for RAN nodes.

Table 7. Target data collection Information.

6.2.2. Trust Algorithms and Enablers

In 5G and 6G scenarios, trust management is an important part of the architecture, as the system needs to ensure that the infrastructure and the services deployed in are secure enough and can be trusted in. For this reason, the Trust Reputation Manager should be developed an entity in charge of evaluating and calculating the reliability of a certain entity, using data from different sources (more specifically, live sources and previously recorded sources). In order to calculate these trust values, a set of parameters are obtained from the enablers, including (but not limited to): date, time of day, ownership of hardware and software, location, network security, physical security, etc. These parameters are shipped from the following enablers:

- Network traffic, virtual machines, hypervisors, and other dynamical deployed entities monitoring services, providing both live and historical data.
- System model/topology of the infrastructure, manifests and other VNF software execution evidence.
- Audits from other entities (remote verifiers) analysing the services of the underlying infrastructure.
- Security policies and Security Service Level Agreements defined in the environment, in order to ensure their compliance.

These parameters are sent to the Trust Reputation Manager using the JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) format, and it calculates a "reputation" value using some weights and fuzzy algorithms (among others).

6.3. Primary workflows

6.3.1. Data Collection and Notifications

The data collection (e.g., abnormal/malicious behaviour information) and security evaluation result notification procedure for an evaluation target such as core NF is described here to enable security and trust evaluation. But the concepts can be extended for other evaluation targets such as RAN nodes and UEs as well. The malicious behaviour related data can be identified related to various events such as predefined service operation violations (e.g., malformed messages), unintended configuration or operational change(s), message requests exceeding configured limits, NF load, NF status and current resource utilization information (if exceeds resource utilization limits) which can be collected as inference data in the form of security logs or reports from the evaluation targets indirectly via the TESP_OAM. For malicious behaviour related new data, the solution involves indirect data collection from the evaluation target(s) via the TESP_OAM to limit the impact (e.g., over the existing event exposure services) by reusing and leveraging TESP_OAM data collection procedure specified in TS 23.288. The data collection and exposure to enable security evaluation for monitoring is shown in *Figure 22*:

Figure 22. Data collection and exposure for security evaluation and monitoring.

1. The TESP enablers (e.g., NWDAF or a dedicated TESP network function) based on operator local policy can collect the data and provide to the external operator function to enable (i.e., assist) security evaluation and monitoring.

2a-b. The TESH enabler can collect data related to NF load and resource utilization by reusing existing data collection procedures specified in TS 23.288 clause 6.5.1 related to NF load (i.e., collection if from NRF) and NF resource usage (i.e., collection from OAM).

2c. The TESH enabler can additionally request TESH_OAM to collect malicious behaviour data related event identifiers for one or more evaluation target NF(s).

2c. The TESH enabler sends to TESH_OAM, a subscribe message (e.g., using the management service offered by the OAM), with evaluation target NF(s) identification information and target event identifier(s) for input data collection.

2d. The TESH_OAM collects the inference data (e.g., as a form of security logs/reports) from the target evaluation NFs based on the events indicated.

NOTE 1a: The normal operations (e.g., predefined SBI service operation message exchanges) can be considered as normal behaviour and as baseline to identify any violations and malformed messages to collect inference data (e.g., any violations to the normal specified behaviour i.e., network function service(s) inputs/outputs specified in TS 23.502 Clause 5.2). Further based on operator implementation the NFs can maintain a threshold (as baseline) for number of message handling related to a NF for a period, if that threshold exceeds, that information can be collected as part of inference data. Based on operator implementation, if any alert arises due to configuration changes, that information can be collected as part of inference data. These data can help to identify any traces (if exist) related to active attacks and passive attacks.

2e. The TESH_OAM provides the collected inference data to the TESH enabler (e.g., NWDAF) with a notification message.

3a. The TESH enabler acts as proxy and can provide the collected data in a request message (e.g., Trust data request) to an external operator managed function (i.e., to enable security evaluation).

NOTE 2: The external operator function/entity, algorithm(s) or intelligence used for the evaluation, security analysis is up to the operator's implementation. The external operator function may be a Security information and event management (SIEM) tool/function.

NOTE 3: The interface used between TESH enabler (e.g., NWDAF), and the external operator function can be a service-based interface which can be consumed by the external operator function taking the role of an AF. If the Operator AF is considered trusted, the AF can directly consume the services offered by the service offered by the TESH enabler. Alternatively, as the AF can be external to the 3GPP domain and if it is residing in an untrusted domain, the data collected by the TESH enabler can be exposed to the AF via the NEF. (e.g., it can be similar to the interface between NEF and external AF).

3b. The external operator function performs security evaluation over the received data and provides the evaluation results in the trust data response message with security evaluation information (i.e., output results e.g., if a threat occurred or not, who is the initiator of the

threat e.g., an identifier), cause (e.g., any attack identified DoS/DDoS/hijack/cyber-attack), and time window. Additionally the management domain function (e.g., TESH_OAM as part of Zero trust management functional block) may assign trust values (e.g., a reliability score such as 1-25% (very low)/26-50% (low)/51-75% (medium)/76-90 (good)/91-100% (high) for the impacted network function due to the identified threat) and provides the trust values as additional output to the TESH.

4a-b. The TESH enabler can provide the security evaluation results (received in step 3b) to the Security and policy enforcement function in a notification message (if it subscribed to TESH) to enable the Security and policy enforcement function to create and enforce access control security policies (e.g., via the NRF by provisioning the NRF with the access control security policies).

7 END-TO-END MULTIDOMAIN MULTI-TENANT 6G SLICING: FIRST ITERATION

This section details the work carried out in the first iteration of Task 3.4 focusing on the design of the RIGOUROUS architectural components involved in meeting the goals defined in this task. Task 3.4 comprises all those activities related to the design and implementation of innovative network slicing mechanisms spanning the whole data plane to provide fine grained control of network traffic in each of the different network segments. In addition, Task 3.4 will provide technologies with enough maturity level to prove their effectiveness against cyber-attacks. Lastly, this task also encompasses the peculiarities associated with the signalling needed to span the mitigation capabilities across multiple domains by enabling the network slicing to be propagated beyond a single administrative domain.

Concerning the role and responsibilities of the partners engaged in this task, UWS is in charge of achieving transversal protection for the edge, transport and core network segments and the physical and virtual resources. UWS also leads the task as well as coordinates the activities between the partners. UMU is responsible for the radio access network segment and its interconnection with the edge. ITAV handles the multi-domain aspect of network slicing. ORO and WINGS track the task with the aim of aligning the delivered enablers with Use Cases 1 and 3, respectively. Finally, LNVO tracks the task for the purpose of aligning the output of T3.3 with the outcomes of this task.

Table 8 lists the functional requirements identified for Task 3.4 describing the expected behaviour and the relationship with the RIGOUROUS framework functional components. The Slice Manager (SM) and the Response Mitigation (RM) component are responsible for providing such functional capabilities.

ID	Requirement description	Verifiability	Origin	Functional components
RIG_FUN_T3.4_080	The system shall have the capability to assign specific application related traffic over their correct slice, such as expected bandwidth, availability, or priority.	Demonstration	Use-case owner	SM, RM

Table 8. Task 3.4 functional requirements.

Regarding non-functional requirements, *Table 9* lists the requirements identified for this task. The Slice Manager is the architectural component responsible of delivering the non-functional requisites for Task 3.4. The design of the architectural components targeted by Task 3.4 has been conducted with the aim of providing both functional and non-functional requirements identified and related to this task.

The primary outcome of this task is to deliver a framework able to provide support for the complete life cycle management and control of End-to-End network slicing capabilities in multi-tenant and multi-domain 6G infrastructures. As shown in *Figure 23*, the life cycle management of a network slice involves different phases such as slice definition, resources allocation, enforcement

of the slice in the data plane, dynamic and agile management of flows attached to the slice, resources release and decommissioning of the slice [15]. The network slice is enforced in the data plane with bandwidth, priority, and availability attributes in order to meet the different use cases and vertical requirements in terms of Quality of Service (QoS) and agreed Service Level Agreements (SLAs).

ID	Requirement description	Verifiability	Origin	Functional components
RIG_IMP_T3.4_1050	The Network Slicing component shall be agnostic of the technology and enforces the slicing rule.	Demonstration	Technology provider	SM

Table 9. Task 3.4 non-functional requirements.

Figure 23. Network Slice life cycle.

7.1. RAN Slicing components

This section provides a description of the design of the RIGOUROUS architectural components involved in providing network slicing capabilities for the Radio Access Network (RAN) segment, i.e. the wireless segment, in multi-domain and multi-tenant 6G infrastructures.

7.1.1. RAN Slicing

As part of its commitment to provide multi-domain and multi-tenant End-to-End network slicing features as a security mechanism to attack mitigation, RIGOUROUS provides network slicing features in the wireless network segment, i.e., the Radio Access Network (RAN). On the one hand, the scarce available resources in this network segment in terms of frequency spectrum are shared between multiple end users and services whilst ensuring the agreed Quality of Service (QoS) parameters. On the other hand, an efficient utilization of the RAN network resources must be made, i.e., the available spectrum must be shared among the users in an optimal and efficient way.

ORO will be the partner in charge of providing the testbed infrastructure to validate and evaluate the network slicing capabilities. Therefore, component integration, and validation and evaluation of use cases related to network slicing will be carried out in ORO's testbed. ORO will deploy in its testbed the NOKIA RAN (Airscale Cloud RAN) based on the 3GPP Release 17 specification. In addition, the Nokia 5G CORE is used by ORO to provide core network functions. RIGOUROUS project will leverage these two components to deliver the network slicing capabilities required in the wireless segment in order to satisfy the demands of the use cases and scenarios defined in WP2.

In a multi-domain context, two 5G infrastructures are interconnected in two ORO sites Bucharest and Lasi. Each one has dedicated computing, automation, and orchestration capabilities. Network slicing, spectrum sharing, authentication, network coding for the virtualized infrastructure is used to preserve privacy and ensure cybersecurity.

The slices are deployed dynamically, and the framework can provide management information by retrieving the 5G slicing characteristics of the facilities (Slice Service Template (SST) based). URLLC or eMBB slices can be deployed with different characteristics for latency or bandwidth, depending on the requirements.

7.2. Non-RAN Slicing components

Non-RAN Slicing covers the wired network segments in a 6G infrastructure, i.e., Edge, Core and Transport. Such network segments have an inherent complexity by design caused by the numerous technologies, protocols, hardware, and network devices involved in shaping the data plane. The implication of such complexity is that a framework with network slicing capabilities for 6G networks should provide the following features:

- Provide an abstract view of the data plane to the management and administration layers, enabling the enforcement of E2E network slices in a uniform manner regardless of the underlying technologies.
- Provide advanced Network Slicing programmability for the various technologies comprising the data plane. That is, to be able to translate high-level technology-agnostic intents into technology-specific instructions for the different points of the data plane where a network slice will be enforced.
- Enablers for the different data plane technologies expected in 6G infrastructures capable of enforcing Security Policies as Network Slices.

The first two previous capabilities are provided by the UWS Slice Manager (SM) component in RIGOUROUS. The third capability, the network slice enabler, is the UWS Network Self-Protection, a OpenVSwitch-based (OVS) [16] software data path with network slicing support for multi-tenant 6G networks. Both components are discussed below, providing a review of the related state of the art and a description of the asset.

7.2.1. UWS Network Self-Protection

6G multi-tenant infrastructures leverage virtualisation combined with Software Defined Networks (SDN) and Network Function Virtualisation (NFV) paradigms to enable multiple tenants to share the same physical infrastructure whilst ensuring the isolation of the traffic of each tenant [17]. As previously stated, the data plane in this kind of infrastructures consists of many different technologies, both software and hardware. Nonetheless, in virtualised multi-tenant deployments, virtual switches play a key role. Virtual switches, as part of the software data path, are the data plane points where the physical infrastructure operated by the Infrastructure Service Provider (ISP) and the virtualised overlay networks deployed on top of the common physical infrastructure converge. Thus, in the context of RIGOUROUS, virtual switches are the adequate data plane points for the deployment of network slicing enablers since it is possible to control the infrastructure's legacy traffic as well as the virtualised traffic coming from the tenants.

As a first stage in the design and implementation of the UWS Network Self-Protection agent, the following characteristics have been targeted as necessary for a software data plane enabler to fulfil the RIGOUROUS requirements regarding network slicing capabilities:

- Enhanced programmability of the data plane allowing the enforcement of advanced Security Policies dynamically in real time.
- Support for the enforcement of fine-grained network slicing in overlay networks with different levels of nested encapsulation.
- Support for network protocols widely adopted in mobile and multi-tenant virtualised deployments such as GTP, VXLAN, GRE or GENEVE used to provide user mobility and tenant traffic isolation.
- Scalability levels to cope with a large number of users simultaneously connected to the infrastructure.

After a comparative review of the existing Software Data paths available, none of them is able to fully provide all these features. The most advanced State-of-the-Art Software Data paths such as Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK) [18], PF Ring [19], Express Data path (XDP) [20], Linux Traffic Control (TC) or Linux IP Tables do not provide network slicing capabilities and they are only capable of classifying and handling traditional IP traffic with no encapsulation. As a result of the review of the current state of the art related to Software Data paths solutions, OpenVSwitch (OVS) has been selected as the baseline for the implementation of the UWS Network Self Protection. The following rationale support this decision:

- OVS is a very-well known platform, and it is considered the de-facto standard virtual switch in virtualised deployments such as cloud computing and data centres.
- OVS is an open-source project widely supported by the developer community and in continuous evolution and development.
- It provides a North Bound Interface (NBI) based on the Open Flow protocol [21]. Open Flow is the most widely used protocol for data plane control and is considered the de-facto standard protocol in Software Defined Networks (SDNs).

- OVS delivers excellent and proven robustness and performance.

Regarding the RIGOUROUS advancements, the development of the UWS Network Self Protection component involves a major extension of the OVS base architecture and functionality to satisfy the demands of the RIGOUROUS project. The following points emerged during the design phase as enhancements to be implemented in the OVS architecture:

- An innovative 6G network traffic classifier extending the traditional classifiers based on IP traffic. This novel traffic will undertake a Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) of the network traffic and will provide a more complex classifier able to handle all data paths expected in 6G infrastructures such as overlay traffic with multiple levels of nested encapsulation.
- Extend de OVS data structures and Open Flow tables with new fields matching the new flow data extracted by the novel 6G traffic classifier.
- Open Flow protocol extension to allow control and management layers a flexible and fine-grained definition of flows. That is, enabling a fine-grained specification of network flows attached to a network slice.
- To extend the command line applications provided in the OVS distribution with the new features as an alternative to the use of Open Flow sockets.
- Extension of the internal and external APIs to support the new Open Flow extensions. For example:
 - The Netlink API for inter-process communication between the OVS daemon in use space and the OVS Linux kernel module.
 - the Open Flow NBI (*ofproto* OVS library) allowing to send and receive extended Open Flow messages from the SDN controller.

7.2.2. Security Slicing

Security Slices are a set of policies that can be applied to a Network Slice in order to provide security services, being the Channel Protection policy the most used one. It provides IPsec protection to the Network Slice, following the policies stated in the Security Slice, as depicted in Section 4.2.1. Security Slicing process allows the Security Orchestrator to deploy E2E network security slices with associated security capabilities, following a policy set. A 5G Security Slice is formed by the slice, an action that determines what the Security Orchestrator must do with the information received, and a secured service (which is usually virtualized). The enforcement of 5G Security Slicing process follows the following steps, depicted in *Figure 24*:

1. The Security Orchestrator receives a set of 5G Security Slicing policies, as defined in section 4.2.1 (which can be proactive or reactive) from either the E2E Security Orchestrator, or from the own domain of the SO.
2. The Security Orchestrator obtains information about the assets and/or enablers in the slice from the Security Agent Manager.
3. The Security Orchestrator communicates with the Intent-based Security Management, in order to translate the policies into configurations for the assets and/or enablers and store them in the Policy Repository.

4. The Security Orchestrator uses the Allocation Engine to generate an enforcement plan using the information from the Security Agent Manager.
5. The Security Orchestrator updates the configuration of the assets and/or enablers in the Data Services.
6. The Security Orchestrator enforces the new configuration into the assets and/or enablers.

Figure 24. Security Orchestration of Security Slices workflow.

```

<ITResourceOrchestration id="mspl_AAAA"
  <ITResource id="mspl_BBBB"
    orchestrationID="mspl_AAAA" tenantID="1">
  <configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration">
    <capability xsi:type="FiveGSecuritySlice">
      <Name>5G_Security_Slice</Name>
      <sliceID>1234</sliceID>
    </capability>
    <configurationRule>
      <configurationRuleAction xsi:type="FiveGSecuritySliceAction">
        <fiveGSecuritySliceActionType>DEPLOY</fiveGSecuritySliceActionType>
        <securedService>
          <service id="98">
            <name>5GService</name>
            <type>VoIP</type>
            <domainID>1</domainID>
          </service>
          <securityRequirements id="CCCC">
            <slolD>1</slolD>
            <slolD>2</slolD>
            <slolD>3</slolD>
          </securityRequirements>
        </securedService>
      </configurationRuleAction>
    </configurationRule>
  </configuration>
</ITResourceOrchestration>
  
```

```
</securityRequirements>
<securityPolicies >
  <msplID>mspl_BBBB</msplID>
  <msplID>mspl_BBBB</msplID>
  <msplID>mspl_DDDD</msplID>
</securityPolicies>
</securedService>
</configurationRuleAction>
<configurationCondition>
  <isCNF>>false</isCNF>
</configurationCondition>
<Name>Rule0</Name>
  <isCNF>>false</isCNF>
</configurationRule>
<Name>Conf0</Name>
</configuration>
</ITResource>
<ITResource id="mspl_EEEE"
  orchestrationID="mspl_AAAA" tenantID="1">
  ...
</ITResource>
</ITResourceOrchestration>
```

The above example in XML format represents an Orchestration Policy which capability is a 5G Security Slice. In this case, the slice is the one represented by id 12, the secured service is VoIP, and the action determines that the Security Orchestrator must deploy the slice. There is also other information related to the Security Slice, such as the domain of the service where it must be deployed, as the treatment of the policy may differ depending on the domain.

One of the policies that a 5G Security Slice can carry on is the Channel Protection. This policy indicates that a secure channel must be created between two entities. Usually, this is performed using IPsec (even though depending on the devices other protocols could be more suitable, for instance DLTS in IoT constrained devices). These policies are later translated from MSPL-OP language to IPsec configuration files (or the equivalent for other protocols) by the Security Orchestrator, and then enforced in the correspondent devices. However, the configurations obtained refining the MSPL-OP policies are not only destined to configuring the final devices, but also can be used to generate configurations for other services, platforms, and controllers.

7.3. E2E and Multi-Domain Network Slicing

7.3.1. E2E Network Slicing

The Slice Manager (SM) is the RIGOUROUS functional block responsible of performing the E2E network slicing capabilities. different capabilities related to slice management in the RIGOUROUS framework. Such capabilities can be summarized as follows:

- Management of the control function of the data plane providing network Slicing capabilities.

- Provide a management of the life cycle of a E2E network slice. That is:
 - Create an End-to-End network slice.
 - Delete an End-to-End network slice.
 - Attach a particular flow to an End-to-End network slice enforced in the data plane.
 - Detach a particular flow to an End-to-End network slice enforced in the data plane.

Figure 25. Slice Manager Initial Design.

Figure 25 shows a design diagram for the Slice Manager functional block. It exposes a northbound interface via API using REST. This northbound interface is being called by the orchestrator and also by the graphical interfaces when an E2E slice need to be created or a set of network flows need to be attached to such pool of available network slices. The E2E slice engine receives the topological information about the network topology available in the infrastructure and also receives the request to create network slices and perform the calculator of all the different endpoint where the network slices need to be enforced in order to create an end-to-end enforcement of the network slice being created. The Topology Database will be populated with data gathered by the Topology Inventory Agent, a distributed asset that will be reported in D4.1. After this calculation is carried out, it interacts with the data plane security enablers to perform the enforcement in each of the end points calculated by the slice engine. The slice manager is a centralized component which perform the enforcing in multiple distributed components in its southbound interfaces which are the security enablers.

The Slice Manager functional block has a sub-functional block entitled Slice Control Agent (SCA) which is distributed and is in charge of providing an abstraction layer of the data plane which enables a technology-agnostic programmability of the various underlying technologies and enablers involved in the different network segments composing the infrastructure such as Edge, Transport and Core.

7.3.2. Multi-Domain Network Slicing

RIGOROUS allows the E2E Network Slice to extend across multiple domains. The Multi-Domain Network Slicing capabilities contemplate different scenarios depending on where each domain is located. Suppose the administrative domains are within the same network operator (e.g., cross-subscriber communication). In that case, the Network Slice definition may allow more stringent Service Level Agreements (SLAs) and enhanced capabilities made possible due to the integration with 5G RAN and core network components. However, suppose the domains are located in different network operators. In that case, the E2E Network Slice is still possible (e.g., in an overlay) but without the functional KPI assurances (e.g., low latency or high reliability) that are only possible within the same network operator.

For the first scenario, ORO developed the architecture to meet the demands of high bandwidth and low latency over the 5G infrastructure. As anticipated, since 3GPP Rel. 16 is the intended design for testbeds, as presented in *Figure 26*, the base of the proposed architecture, consists of a Virtualized Infrastructure environment replicated in two domains: the NF communication framework with REST APIs, along with the 5G Access RAN and the Core Network functionalities. The E2E architecture's scope includes designing the 5G E2E architectural reference and deploying key points to meet security and accessibility needs. The network interfaces connecting the testbeds to the 5G open testbed implementation framework in VITAL-5G are also included in the suggested architecture:

- Management information, acting like a GET function to retrieve the 5G slicing characteristics of the facilities (SST-based)
- Collecting the local facilities working like PUSH network and service KPIs, monitoring the facilities-related parameters through Kafka broker

Figure 26. ORO Testbed Design Architecture.

The design approach for the second scenario follows federation agreements and a fallback to inter-domain approaches. When the Network Slicing Orchestrator has federated agreements with other domains controlled by another Network Slicing Orchestrator, East/West-bound interfaces are used to maintain proper Network Slice operation within the functional KPI assurances made possible by the federation agreements. However, if the resources in the other administrative domain(s) do not have any explicit federation agreement, a virtual connection will be established across the domains, and the Network Slice Orchestration will fall under the orchestrator that now controls resource pools in different domains. There are no guarantees for functional KPIs when dealing with virtual links over uncontrolled networks (e.g., low latency or high reliability).

For instance, the OpenSlice Network Slice Orchestrator already contemplates native multi-domain network slicing at service level, as illustrated in *Figure 27*.

Figure 27. OpenSlice Network Slice with native multi-domain network slicing at service level.

7.4. Primary Workflows

This section contains sequences diagrams illustrating how the RIGOUROUS architectural components interact and cooperate to provide network slicing capabilities.

7.4.1. Network Slice Management and Control

The below sequence diagram shown in *Figure 28* depicts the interaction and communication between the different RIGOUROUS architectural components (functional modules and services) in order to enforce an End-to-End (E2E) network slice in the data plane. The diagram matches the proactive workflow as presented in deliverable D2.1. That is, the enforcement of an E2E slice in the data plane is performed in a proactive manner where the domain administrator triggers the action.

The reactive workflow described in deliverable D2.1, as an automatic system's response to mitigate a cyber-attack, will be discussed thoroughly in WP4, dealing with an automatic reactive loop for AI-driven anomaly detection and mitigation, where the components of the reactive plane play an essential role.

As it can be observed, the functional blocks involved in the below flow diagram belongs to the design, operational, and monitoring and analytical planes. As an example, this flow diagram explains the creation of a network slice. The interaction between architectural components to provide support for other phases of the life cycle of a E2E network slice such as properties modification or deletion is similar and the RIGOUROUS functional blocks involved are the same.

In step 1, the domain/network/system administrator defines in a human-friendly manner a Security Policy (SP) or Security Service Level Agreement (SSLA) using the Intent Based security formal modelling tool (SMUI). Then, in 2, the SP/SSLA is sent to the Intent-Based Security Management (ISM) module using an abstract high-level language for User-centric model representation. In step 3, The ISM module examines potential conflicts between the new security policy to be applied and the existing security policies already enforced in the infrastructure. If no conflict is identified, in step 4, the ISM sends the requested E2E security policy to the Security Orchestrator (OS).

In multi-domain scenarios, the new security policy could be an E2E policy involving several single domains. In this case, in step 5 of the flow diagram, the E2E Security Orchestrator service of the functional block contacts the other domain-level Security Orchestrator services of other Security Management Domains (SMDs) to enable them to apply the domain-level security policies in their respective domain. Each one of the SO for each SMD involved in the enforcement of the SSLA/SP relies on its own ISM for checking potential conflicts leading to the impossibility of fulfilling the SLA (in the same way as the E2E SO does in step 3).

Figure 28. Sequence Diagram for creating a E2E network slicing for single and multi-domain 6G infrastructures.

In steps 6 and 7, the SO sends a request to the Data Services component (DS) to retrieve information about different resources such as available MANOS, Slice Managers, or allocation managers. The SO also asks the DS component about the specific enablers, data plane agents or assets on which the E2E network slice is to be enforced as well as topological information. In steps 8 and 9, then SO then sends a query to the Zero Trust Manager (ZTM) asking for the indexes and scores of the different services and resources involved across the different network segments in the deployment of the Network Slice. This will allow to establish priorities in the deployment of the slices that are enforced or are going to be enforced.

At this point, the E2E network slice implementing the Security Policy defined by the domain administrator in step 1 can be effectively enforced in the data plane of the infrastructure. Then, the slice creation can be performed in different ways depending on the infrastructure topology, the network segment, and the different underlying technologies available in the data plane (notice the different components located in the 6G infrastructure box in the flow diagram), such as:

- Firewall rules deployed on a Virtual Firewall (vFirewall).
- API offered by MANO services (new chain of security VNFs).
- Slice Managers providing extended programmability of the data plane.
- SDN controllers with Network Slicing capabilities.

In the example depicted in the flow diagram, the network slice is enforced via the Slice Manager component. In step 10, the SO sends an intent message to the Slice Manager with the information needed to create the network slice. This message is technology independent. That is, the Slice Manager provides to the SO an abstract view of the data plane, hiding the underlying technologies co-existing in the data plane. In step 11, the Slice Manager enforces the network slice. To achieve this, the SM transforms the received technology-agnostic intent message into a set of actions in the specific technology of the security data plane agent where the network slice is going to be enforced (step 12).

Finally, once the network slice has been created, an ACK message is sent back to the SO to report the successful result of the enforcement (steps 13 and 14).

7.5. Alignment to Related Tasks

This subsection outlines the follow-up work undertaken to make sure that the progress reported for task 3.4 is consistent and harmonized with other project work packages and tasks in terms of integration and expected outcomes:

- Alignment with use cases and scenarios defined in WP2 where the outcomes of Task 3.4 will be deployed, especially in Use Cases 1 and 3.
- Alignment with Task 3.3 outcomes (Zero Trust and Smart Management RIGOUROUS architectural component).

7.5.1. Alignment to Use Cases

This section tracks the progress made in task 3.4 in order to make sure the different network slicing enablers deployed across the data plane are fully aligned and consistent with the specifications and requirements of use cases 1 and 3 defined in deliverable D2.2. In particular, this follow-up monitors that the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Value Indicators (KVI) defined for each use case as well as other required features of the components such as responsiveness, scalability, interface compatibility or availability among others are met.

Use case 1 addresses the feasibility of the RIGOUROUS framework for providing protection of 6G-enabled services against cyber threats using network slicing as mitigation approach. To this end, three different scenarios will be deployed where different mitigation approaches will be implemented as described in Deliverable 2.2.

Regarding use case 3, in terms of domains, this use case considers either the diverse applications and systems that the utilities have or the different subsystems existing in the same application and system (e.g., IoT devices, gateways, edge, cloud and the networks among the previous parts). Two threat scenarios covering the gas energy network and utilities sectors as described in deliverable D2.2 will assess the suitability of the RIGOUROUS components.

Slicing is particularly useful for the third threat scenario of Use case 1. ORO will incorporate the UMU Security Orchestration to combine several models that could enhance overall robustness and decision making in terms of orchestration and slice management. The Orchestrator may be used to implement mitigation actions to isolate the attacker in a DDoS assault, and it can also be used to enforce slicing as a mitigation tool. In order to enable quick slice management and service replication across unaffected areas of ORO's testbed infrastructure, ORO will incorporate Amazon's Slice Manager and Slice management Agent into our present MANO capabilities for the third threat scenario, which considers a DDoS.

Use case 3 focuses on the security of Utilities operations, and network slicing can be very useful as it allows the division of the network into logically isolated networks that can be seen as a slice. Especially scenario 2 which is about DDoS attacks in Utilities networks, Security Orchestration can be used in order to allow dynamic allocation and management of network slice resources, such as computing, storage, and network connectivity, to facilitate timely detection of threats from several models, and in this way to ensure the security of the network.

7.5.1.1. ORO use case Testbed

ORO aims to validate the RIGOUROUS platform's ability to provide trust for security in telecom infrastructures, making it appropriate to be exposed to security risks associated with 5G and B5G infrastructure.

ORO can provide two interconnected 5G infrastructures in Iasi and Bucharest in multidomain setting, with both sites being accessed remotely. In order to guarantee privacy-preserving technology, network slicing, spectrum sharing, authentication, and network coding are used for the virtualized infrastructure.

The testbed, presented in *Figure 29* supports cybersecurity threat detection and response functionalities, such as DDoS Detection and Mitigation or signature-based Network-based Intrusion Detection and Prevention. On the computational components, host-based agents can be installed to provide more precise enhanced detection and response capabilities.

The testbed is fully a 5G SA 3GPP Rel.16 infrastructure with plans to be Rel.17 compliant. It employs open software tools, advanced programmable network solutions, MANO functions, security functions, and large computing resources.

The ORO testbed supports Infrastructure as a Code, network, and application development, testing and deployment through CI\CD with Jenkins and Ansible and allows for dynamic slice implementation, with eMBB and URLLC slice capabilities.

Figure 29. ORO testbed.

7.5.2. Alignment to Zero Trust and Smart Security Management (LNVO)

The purpose of this sub-section is to track and monitor Task 3.4 in order to make sure the outputs of this task are completely aligned and consistent with the outputs provided by Task 3.3. That is, the outcomes of Task 3.4 have to be aligned with the algorithms and service enablers previously described in this document in section 6 about Zero Trust and Smart Security Management.

For secure deployment and maintenance of end-to-end network slices in multi-domain multi-tenant 6G network, the trust scores of the network entities/functions play a critical role in the network security policy enforcement. The zero trust services and enablers intend to provide trust score based on the behavioural analysis during the network security monitoring (which also includes the network slices). The security orchestrator involved in creation and management of the slices takes the TESP provided trust score (per network entity or slice) into account to configure and enforce security policies for various network slice operation specific actions listed below (but not an exhaustive list):

- Configuration of Network Slices
- Selection of Network Slices
- Re-selection of Network Slices
- Slice Isolation
- Network Slice Security Context sharing restrictions.
- Network Slice termination

8 NEXT STEPS

In this deliverable the basic design and workflow of the components were described, which are involved in assuring the multi-domain automated security orchestration, trust-management, and deployment. The next phase of the task is to be continued in D3.2 with prototype designs and implementation, furthermore, to be complemented with experimental setup and potential results. Deliverable D3.2 will be hence aligned to this deliverable and will have the tentative improvements as listed in *Table 10* below:

Task	Asset	Current status	Next step	Partners involved
Human-centric security and privacy modelling and onboarding	Policy-based network management	Design and workflow of Policy based network management and policy translation components.	Implementation of Privacy Quantification and Management API. Deployment and testing phases of Network Application onboarding. Identify the configuration space available to move the attack surface without service disruption.	ITAV
AI-driven cross-domain Security and Privacy orchestration in IoT-edge-cloud continuum	Security Orchestration	Design of Orchestration flow with conflict and dependency detection.	Design orchestration algorithms. Develop the orchestration for security slices.	UMU
	FL for Anomaly Detection Orchestration	Design of policy model for Orchestration of FL entities. Design of proactive and reactive FL orchestration process along with FL based anomaly detection.	Develop the FL orchestration	UMU
	Bootstrapping and onboarding	Design and workflow of Zero touch Device bootstrapping. Design and workflow of Trusted Application Onboarding.	Provide the technical specifications for the report.	LNVO
		Design of Enrolment using privacy-preserving ABC credentials.	describe technical specifications and integrations with bootstrapping process	UMU

Zero trust and Smart security management	Trust Evaluation and Enabler	Design and workflow of Trust Evaluation and Enabler Service Function. Design of Trust Algorithms.	API design and integration along with trust score as output for any component in the network.	LNVO
End-to-End multidomain multi-tenant 6G slicing	Slice Manager	SotA Analysis, Design, and architectural prototyping.	First version of a functional prototype.	UWS
	Network Self Protection Component	SotA Analysis, Design, and architectural prototyping.	First version of a functional prototype.	UWS

Table 10. Summary of WP3 current status and next steps.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this deliverable, the initial outcomes compiled from all the tasks in WP3 are reported, presenting the first iteration of analysis and design of the enablers and components for all the involved subsystems including Human-Centric security and privacy modelling and onboarding, AI-driven cross-domain Security and Privacy orchestration in IoT-edge-cloud continuum, Zero Trust and Smart security management, and End-to-End multidomain multi-tenant 6G slicing.

For each of the subsystems, this deliverable has presented a review of the existing relevant work, which has been utilised to inform the design of the corresponding subsystem, considering pushing innovations beyond the state of the art in this design phase. Informed by the literature as well as the outcomes from WP2 on the high-level architecture of the whole system including the interactions among the subsystems in the scope of WP3 and the concerned functional and non-functional requirements, the components within each of the have been carefully devised and described in detail. The initial primary workflows have then been investigated to show how each of the subsystem would operate.

As indicated in the next steps, the design presented in this deliverable will pave the way for the prototyping of the components and the subsystems.

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